

Technical Note on Quality Assessment for BlackSky

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1. EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Figure 1-1: BlackSky image of Salon de Provence, France, pilot training school.

BlackSky offers Very High Resolution (**VHR**) Multispectral (**MS**) and Panchromatic (**PAN**) imagery acquired with four satellites positioned in two different orbits; low earth orbit and sun synchronous orbit. As part of a constellation, this configuration ensures the delivery of data in a timely manner.

The payload of BlackSky satellites is the Harris Spaceview small satellite imaging system embedding a high Charge-Coupled Device (**CCD**) colour camera. This high-quality colour camera allows to access to finer details in the scene, since the Ground Sampling Distance (**GSD**) of the optical system at Nadir is within 1.0 m.

The target applications of BlackSky imagery is data analytics and interpretation. Moreover, BlackSky offers on demand intelligence services strongly based on Artificial Intelligence (**AI**) and Machine Learning (**ML**) techniques.

In this context, the handling of a large data volume is possible if, and only if, the data quality is appropriate, knowing that any wrong data quality pixel might introduce artefacts in the data modelling process (learning, detection, prediction, classification).

For these reasons, the BlackSky company provides some simple very high spatial resolution products including notably;

- A pixel-based data quality assurance mask as part of the quality assurance information, flagging pixels contaminated with thin or thick cloud;
- An accurate 3-dimensional generic geometric model, by means of Rational Polynomial Coefficients (**RPC**).

Moreover, the BlackSky company introduces the notion of “anthro processing level”. The “anthro” processing aims to adjust the image’s colour balance and enhance the image’s contrast [RD-3]. Compared to legacy missions (Landsat / Sentinel 2), the Digital Numbers (**DN**) in “anthro processing level” images are not calibrated from a radiometric point of view,

and conversion from DN to Top of Atmosphere (**TOA**) measurement is not straightforward and sometimes not possible, restricting de facto the potential uses of the imagery.

Consequently, the scope of the EDAP activity has been to perform data assessments focused on the product format, the image quality and the geometric quality of non-ortho and ortho products.

The product format is rather simple and most efforts have been spent on checking the Quality Assurance (**QA**) mask consistency. The QA mask reports valid, cloudy and saturated pixels:

- The valid pixels (except the defective or dead ones) are results of several checks performed by the calibration team on a monthly basis, these results are captured as part of auxiliary information involved in the product processing.
- The cloudy pixels are results of automatic algorithms running during the product processing that discern thin and thick cloud.

The EDAP assessment concludes that the quality of the QA mask is correct, in particular for the flagging of cloud. However, the flagging of defective / dead pixels is not perfect and depends on the potential lag between calibration team results and updates in an operational context.

The image quality is a critical aspect for a VHR optical mission dedicated to interpretation and object recognition. This data quality item has been assessed by adopting two distinct approaches:

- Visual inspection method derived from image interpretability techniques: comparing a set of ground target objects seen by the BlackSky mission and seen by reference missions;
- Quantitative method to assess the Signal to Noise Ratio (**SNR**) and the Modulation Transfer Function (**MTF**).

The EDAP assessment concludes that the image quality of the Multispectral (**MS**) bands is fit for application purposes. Several comments mostly raised with reference to image processing algorithms might be formulated:

- The data quality of the Panchromatic (**PAN**) band is degraded compared to the quality of MS bands, the PAN band is heavily contaminated with noise.
- Some very bright or very dark real scene objects cannot be observed in the BlackSky images because of filtering.
- The MTF / SNR results are correct and image quality is fit for object detection or recognition.
- The Edge Spread Function (**ESF**) results are very interesting showing ringing effects due to image processing filter, it confirms observations made in the visual inspection activity.

The geometric quality of imagery has been assessed alongside classical absolute geolocation, temporal geolocation and interband registration validation items. The geometric quality is also a critical parameter for VHR optical data. For this reason, the two delivered processing levels, non-ortho and ortho have been thoroughly investigated. The non-ortho products have been processed with a specific procedure and results compared

to the standard BlackSky ortho products. It is worth noting that the scene geographic extent is relatively small and does not allow for full use the set of Ground Control Point (**GCP**) derived from a test field survey. To overcome this issue, a raster reference has been prepared and involved in the geometric assessment related to absolute accuracy with matching. Large systematic errors are observed in the Level 1C (**L1C**) standard product. It is possibly due to using a generic model (RPC) to perform ortho processing. Unfortunately, the accuracy of the RPCs is also not very high; a larger systematic bias is observed; however, the precision is better. Regarding the precision of the geolocation, the assessment results show that it might be improved when using a specific digital elevation model (ALOS DEM AW3d30¹ herein) instead of the standard one (NASA Shuttle Radar Topographic Mission (**SRTM**)) used in BlackSky product processing.

¹ <https://www.eorc.jaxa.jp/ALOS/en/aw3d30/index.htm>

2. INTRODUCTION

This document is the Technical Note (TN) on Quality Assessment report for the BlackSky mission.

The quality assessment provides a series of checks on the product format, product metadata, geometric calibration and radiometric calibration on a small sample of products. It is important to note that it is possible that these products have been updated since the analysis described in this document.

The quality assessment performed here is in accordance with the assessment guidelines provided in the EarthNet Data Assessment Pilot (EDAP) project [RD-1] and the guidelines tailored for optical missions [RD-2].

2.1 Reference Documents

The following is a list of reference documents with a direct bearing on the content of this proposal. Where referenced in the text, these are identified as [RD-n], where 'n' is the number in the list below:

- RD-1. EDAP.REP.001 Generic EDAP Best Practice Guidelines, 1.1 23 May 2019
- RD-2. EDAP.REP.002 Optical Mission Quality Assessment Guidelines, v1.0, 16 October 2019.
- RD-3. BlackSky, Imagery Product Specification Version 2b.2.0 (received in March 2020)
- RD-4. SPACEVIEW 24/35/42, Small Satellite Imaging Solutions, Harris Advertising
- RD-5. EDAP.MEM.013 EDAP BlackSky Visual Inspection Report, v0.1, 15 Sept 2020
- RD-6. IDEAS+-VEG-OQC-REP-2648, IDEAS+ Landsat MSS QA Band Technical Note, v3.0, 9 November 2018
- RD-7. Zaroni, "IKONOS Signal-to-Noise Ratio Estimation", March 25-27, 2002, JACIE Workshop, 2002 <https://ntrs.nasa.gov/search.jsp?R=20040004380>
- RD-8. Françoise Viallefont-Robinet, Dennis Helder, Renaud Fraisse, Amy Newbury, Frans van den Bergh, Donghan Lee, Sébastien Saunier. Comparison of MTF measurements using edge method: towards reference data set. Optics Express, Optical Society of America, 2018, 26 (26), pp.33625-33648. (hal-02055611)
- RD-9. S. Saunier, P. Goryl, G. Chander, M. Bouvet, R. Santer and S. Kocaman, "Radiometric, geometric and image quality assessment of the ALOS AVNIR-2 and PRISM sensors," TGRS, 48(10), 3855-3866 (2010).
- RD-10. K. Kohm, "Modulation transfer function measurement method and results for the Orbview-3 high resolution imaging satellite," Proceedings of ISPRS, Istanbul, Turkey (2004).
- RD-11. Cournet, M., A. Giros, L. Dumas, J. M. Delvit, D. Greslou, F. Languille, G. Blanchet, S. May, et J. Michel. « 2D Sub-Pixel Disparity Measurement Using QPEC / Medicis ». ISPRS - International Archives of the Photogrammetry, Remote Sensing and Spatial

Information Sciences XLI-B1 (3 juin 2016): 291-98.

<https://doi.org/10.5194/isprsarchives-XLI-B1-291-2016>.

RD-12. CEOS Analysis Ready Data for Land Surface Reflectance (CARD4L-SR) Product

Family Specification, Version 5.0, 8 June 2020,

http://ceos.org/ard/files/PFS/SR/v5.0/CARD4L_Product_Family_Specification_Surface_Reflectance-v5.0.pdf

2.2 Glossary

The following acronyms and abbreviations have been used in this Report.

AC	Across-track
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AL	Along-track
APL	Auxiliary Payload
ATBD	Algorithm Theoretical Baseline Document
CCD	Charge-Coupled Device
CFA	Colour Filter Array
DEM	Digital Elevation Model
DN	Digital Numbers
EDAP	EARTHNET Data Assessment Pilot
EELV	Evolved Expendable Launch Vehicle
ESF	Edge Spread Function
ESPA	EELV Secondary Payload Adapter
EXIF	Exchangeable Image File Format
FWHM	Full Width at Half Maximum
GCP	Ground Control Point
GSD	Ground Sampling Distance
HR	High Resolution
IFOV	Instantaneous Field of View
L1B	Level 1B
L1C	Level 1C
LOESS	Locally Estimated Scatterplot Smoothing

LSF	Line Spread Function
ML	Machine Learning
MS	Multispectral , Multi Spectral
MTF	Modulation Transfer Function
NCC	Normalized Cross Correlation
NIIRS	National Imagery Interpretability Rating Scale
NITF	National Imagery Transmission Format
NPL	National Physical Laboratory
PAN	Panchromatic , Panchromatic
PDI	Product Data Item
PHR	Pleiades High Resolution
PICS	Pseudo Invariant Calibration Site
POI	Point Of Interest
QA	Quality Assurance
RER	Relative Edge Response
RPC	Rational Polynomial Coefficients
SNR	Signal to Noise Ratio
SRTM	Shuttle Radar Topographic Mission
TN	Technical Note
TOA	Top of Atmosphere
UDM	Usable Data Mask
UTM	Universal Transverse Mercator
VHR	Very High Resolution

3. EDAP QUALITY ASSESSMENT

3.1 EDAP Maturity Matrix

This preliminary assessment was performed following the EDAP quality assessment guidelines written by the National Physical Laboratory (NPL) [RD-1], and the results summarised in Table 3-1 and detailed in Section 4. It is considered as a 'preliminary assessment' as it was prepared using a small sample of products over specific calibration sites.

Table 3-1: BlackSky Quality Maturity Matrix

Product Information	Product Generation	Ancillary Information	Uncertainty Characterisation	Validation
Product Details	Sensor Calibration & Characterisation Pre-Flight	Product Flags	Uncertainty Characterisation Method	Reference Data Representativeness
Product Availability & Accessibility	Uncertainty Sources Included	Reference Data Quality		
Product Format		Uncertainty Values Provided	Validation Method	
User Documentation			Geolocation Uncertainty	Validation Results
Metrological Traceability Documentation				

Key
Not Assessed
Not Assessable
Basic
Intermediate
Good
Excellent
Information not public

3.2 Summary of Quality Assessment

The summary of the activities performed for BlackSky products listed in APPENDIX B is shown in Table 3-2.

Table 3-2: Executive Summary

Assessment	Results
<p>Product Details and Visual Assessment</p>	<p>BlackSky imagery allows accurate extraction of specific objects observed with similar missions proposing the same instrument / image GSD.</p> <p>Due to post processing and data origin, the quality of imagery varies from date to date; exhibiting more or less noise, saturation, ringing etc. This might be considered as a shortcoming of the products.</p> <p>The BlackSky operation team monitors the health of the instrument and maintains, in a configuration calibration table, where detector anomalies are flagged. This information is included in the quality mask.</p> <p>The information in the mask looks consistent, but due to incomplete documentation and inconsistent georeferencing between the Usable Data Mask (UDM) and image products, it has been difficult to assess.</p> <p>The content of the mask is good, delimitating cloud cover and an array of image anomalies, although no reference is provided within product documentation regarding UDM values. Where information is available, there is a mismatch between mask values and with further investigation the layer uses binary values to present inconsistent pixels.</p> <p>The percentage of cloud provided in the product metadata is lower than that delineated within the UDM Cloud layer by ~1%, omitting thinner non-classified cloud.</p> <p>The quality of the PAN band is highly degraded compared to the MS bands.</p>
<p>Geometric accuracy</p>	<p>Absolute Geolocation Accuracy</p> <p>The limited geographical coverage of the BlackSky product footprint did not allow to collect a lot of GCPs in the scene; 4 GCPs per product as a maximum number, which limits the certainty of the results.</p> <p>A geometric raster reference has been prepared and the accuracy results received from a GCP set (test field survey) have been confirmed with results from the image matching.</p> <p>For the sample dataset, the absolute accuracy of the BlackSky geometry is 28 m (CE90), the precision of the results exceeding 20 m in the both the Easting and Northing directions.</p> <p>Note that the accuracy of RPC coefficients provided within the Level 1B (L1B) product is less accurate compared to the Level 1C product. However, use of RPCs allows for control of the Digital Elevation Model</p>

Assessment	Results
	<p>(DEM) used for orthorectification, and therefore, the precision achieved is generally better with RPC coefficient (even if accuracy is degraded).</p> <p>Relative – Temporal Geolocation Accuracy</p> <p>The relative temporal accuracy is below 10.0 m (CE90) and is not stable with time. The delivered data has been observed with various nadir point angles. For images observed with < 20° off-nadir angles, the co-registration was below 5.00 m CE90.</p> <p>Interband</p> <p>The MS interband accuracy is very good; within 0.01 pixel. We note a static shift when PAN band is involved in the assessment.</p>
<p>Image quality</p>	<p>Visual inspection</p> <p>In depth analysis, based on Points Of Interest (POI), shows that images are fit for the purposes of object extraction. Comparing with a better spatially resolved reference image, it has been observed that in some cases, objects are not detected within the BlackSky imagery. It is particularly true for objects displayed in the image that are part of a dark intensity image patch. The “anthro” processing further smooths uniform image patches and can, consequently, remove some object details.</p> <p>SNR</p> <p>There is no SNR specification proposed by the data provider. The computed SNR does not change greatly depending on the spectral band. The SNR is usually associated to a radiance level in the community. Absolute calibration is not applied to BlackSky data. Also, method is more complex including a scene-based calibration. The SNR is generally high for all RGB bands and comparable to those of similar VHR missions. It confirms that post processing, aiming at reducing noise while increasing the image contrast, is working as expected.</p> <p>MTF</p> <p>The transfer functions of the system have been estimated and main quality parameter derived. The MTF at Nyquist is above 0.08, which is fully in agreement with the specification for such a system including Bayer Colour Filter Array as optics. The quality of the panchromatic band is degraded compared to the MS ones.</p> <p>The “anthro” processing increases the image contrast with the same quantity of information, with the risk of creating “halos” around boundaries and noise over uniform image areas. The analysis of MTF curves reveals the boost of some frequencies due to sharpening, and also the presence of aliasing, even if anti-aliasing is applied.</p> <p>Note that these results are limited to the BSG-103 spacecraft.</p>

4. DETAILED EDAP QUALITY ASSESSMENT

4.1 Product Information

The Product Information section covers the top-level product descriptive information, product format, and the supporting documentation.

The product detail information in the JSON product metadata is listed in the table below, with parameter value given when available in the product itself or parameter value available in documentation.

Any required information is missing. There is a minimum set of information available. It is worth noting that important aspect related to radiometric processing or pixel spacing should be documented. For these reasons, the Product Information EDAP grade is “Basic”.

Product Details	
Product Name	<i>BlackSky Non-Ortho Product including RPC (GeoTIFF, NITF) BlackSky Ortho Product (GeoTIFF, NITF)</i>
Sensor Name	<i>Global-[1-3] (Harris SpaceView 24 payload)</i>
Sensor Type	<i>Framing Camera with BAYER Cooler Filter Array (MS + PAN)</i>
Product Version Number	<i>In the JSON Metadata "imageSpecVersion": "1.0.0",</i>
Processor Name / Version	<i>In the JSON Metadata "processingVersion": "master-c0a713b82",</i>
Product ID	<i><SensorName>_<SatelliteID>_<AcquisitionDate>_<AcquisitionTime>_ < ImageID> Example: BSG-104-20191025-094224-528654 Full list in APPENDIX B</i>
Processing level of product	<i>Level 1B / Level 1C ('ortho' / 'non ortho') Information is not directly accessible from the product metadata Information given as part of the product filename ('ortho' / 'non ortho') In addition, metadata flag indicates if data is 'georeferenced' and/or 'orthorectified'.</i>
Measured Quantity Name	<i>Digital Number</i>
Measured Quantity Units	<i>N/A</i>
Stated Measurement Quality	<i>Information on the radiometric measurement quality is unavailable Information on the geometric quality of product is indicated within the JSON metadata: there is the accuracy related to co-registration processing and the details on ground control point set involved in this processing (image coordinates, geographical coordinates, elevation above ellipsoid).</i>
Spatial Resolution	<i>The spatial resolution of the image depends on the satellite height and pointing (0.9 m -> 1.3 m).</i>

	<i>The Ground Sampling Distance is given in the JSON metadata. However, the pixel spacing, in case of orthorectified product; is not report in the JSON metadata.</i>
Spatial Coverage	<i>The spatial coverage depends on the mission. The dimension of image frame is report as part of JSON metadata (width, height). The geographic extent of the scene footprint is not report.</i>
Temporal Resolution	<i>On demand image (daily revisit with the constellation) depending on the location.</i>
Temporal Coverage	<i>On demand image (daily revisit with the constellation) depending on the location.</i>
Point of Contact	www.e-geos.it
Product locator (DOI/URL)	<i>none</i>
Conditions for access and use	<i>Not for redistribution without BlackSky's consent</i>
Limitations on public access	<i>Strictly confidential</i>
Product Abstract	<i>Full product description available at: https://www.blacksky.com/</i>

There is no evidence that FAIR Data is followed because the EDAP did not access to a catalogue for data selection purposes. For this reason, the EDAP grade of **Product Availability & Accessibility** is 'Not assessable'.

Availability & Accessibility	
Compliant with FAIR principles	<i>No</i>
Data Management Plan	<i>Not available to users</i>
Availability Status	<i>Available for download previous commercial license</i>

The imagery product specification document is strictly confidential [RD-3]. This document does not give a description of each product format parameters and does not refer to a metadata standard. Furthermore, the compliance to INSPIRE metadata is not followed. For these reasons the EDAP grade of **Product Format** is 'Basic'.

Product Format	
Product File Format	<i>Data encoding is standard GeoTIFF & NITF formats, and JSON metadata files</i>
Metadata Conventions (JSON)	<pre>{ "id" : "", "acquisitionDate" : "", "sensorName" : "", "gsd" : , "geometry" : { "type" : "Polygon", "coordinates" : [] }, "cloudCoverPercent" ;, "offNadirAngle" : , "sunElevation" : , "sunAzimuth" : , "satelliteElevation" : ,</pre>

	<pre>"satelliteAzimuth" : , "georeferenced" : , "orthorectified" : , "width" : , "height" : , "processingVersion" : "master-c0a713b82", "targetType" : "platform_orders", "estimatedCE90" : , "bitsPerPixel" : 12, "imageSpecVersion" : "1.0.0", "fractionSaturated" : 0.0, "numberRegistrationPoints" : , "registrationPoints" : [], "gemini" : { "catalogImageld" : "", "imageld" : ""}</pre>
Analysis Ready Data?	<p>The CARD4L-SR threshold (Minimum) requirements [RD-12] for the general metadata and the Per Pixel metadata are not met, with some major 'non compliancy':</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No radiometric corrections, • Algorithms are not identified in the metadata, • Auxiliary data are not identified in the metadata.

INSPIRE metadata records shall be encoded in XML format valid against one of the following XML Schemas:

- [CSW2 AP ISO] XML Schema²,
- [ISO 19139] XML Schema as available in the ISO repository³,
- [ISO 19139] XML Schema as available in the OGC schema repository⁴.

The BlackSky metadata records are not encoded following INSPIRE recommendations. Furthermore, recommended information as Point of Contact, Licence details, Product abstract and Product locator are missing from the metadata.

The product user guide is disclosed to the user under agreement and is up to date. The product user guide approach is minimalist. The geolocation processing and cloud score assessment algorithms are briefly discussed. The "anthro" processing is an important characteristic of the BlackSky product that is not addressed. Furthermore, the level of information available elsewhere is poor, notably there is no documentation shared in the various remote sensing / GIS conferences (proceedings, presentations). The web portal of the data provider does not disclose additional information.

²[http://inspire.ec.europa.eu/draft-schemas/inspire-md-schemas/importing the srv namespace for encoding service metadata and referring to GML version 3.2.1 available in the OGC schema repository](http://inspire.ec.europa.eu/draft-schemas/inspire-md-schemas/importing-the-srv-namespace-for-encoding-service-metadata-and-referring-to-gml-version-3.2.1-available-in-the-ogc-schema-repository) (as defined in the schemas at <http://inspire.ec.europa.eu/draft-schemas/inspire-md-schemas/srv/1.0/>).

³<http://www.isotc211.org/2005/gmd/gmd.xsd>referring to GML version 3.2.1 available in the ISO schema repository.

⁴<http://schemas.opengis.net/iso/19139/20070417/gmd/gmd.xsd>referring to GML version 3.2.1 available in the OGC schema repository,

As, the product user guide is somehow limited and there is no ATBD, the EDAP grade of **User Documentation** is 'Basic'.

User Documentation		
Document	Reference	QA4ECV Compliant
Product User Guide	Available upon request & under license	Partially – user cases and validation missing.
ATBD	Not available to users. Some Algorithm information are given in the user guide [RD-3].	Missing documentation

There is no traceability chain documented. For this reason, the EDAP grade for **Metrological Traceability** is 'Not Assessable'.

4.2 Product Generation

The Product Generation section covers the processing steps undertaken to produce the data. As mentioned previously, the data provider delivered Level 1 non-orthorectified and orthorectified data products.

There is neither documentation about pre-flight calibration activities nor evidence that the performance of the mission is monitored (i.e. the post-launch calibration and characterisation activities). It is worth noting that Harris [RD 4] should be, as instrument provider, responsible for maintaining performance of data acquisition chain.

The informal discussions that have been had with the data provider previously (email exchange) indicate data quality operations are performed routinely and important anomalies, such as a dead detector, are monitored routinely also.

The additional processing algorithms involved in the product generation have been checked with respect to methods shortly described in [RD-3] and also with respect to the independent EDAP assessments. The quality of these four product generation components; Rational Polynomial Coefficient generation, orthorectification processing, QA mask and "Anthro" processing is considered as correct. This additional processing steps are documented and all significant additional processing steps are fit for stated purposes. For these reasons, the EDAP grade of '**Additional processing**' is 'Intermediate'.

4.3 Ancillary Information

Thanks to the product Usable Data Mask file, there is a comprehensive set of well documented product flags reporting on detector quality state and cloud cover. As shown in this assessment, the accuracy of this information might be improved as product flags exist and are well documented [RD 3], notably cloud score, and so the EDAP grade of '**Product Flags**' is therefore 'Intermediate'.

Product Flags	
Product Flag Documentation	File Mask Specification is available on request.

Comprehensiveness of Flags	Cloud mask, detector failure mask
----------------------------	-----------------------------------

Regarding ancillary data itself, all information required to properly define the primary measured data is considered as minimal: the viewing geometries are given at the scene centre, and sensor spectral response shared on demand by the data provider. These data are not provided together with uncertainty quantified. Additional information such as meteorological data is not provided. The ancillary data is considered as not available. As consequence, the EDAP grade for **'Ancillary Data'** is *'Not Assessable'*.

4.4 Uncertainty Characterisation

BlackSky measurements are not accompanied by evaluated uncertainty estimates. In addition, there is no documentation mentioning the intention of the data provider to go into this direction. Therefore, it is not possible to state that a specific mission's uncertainty characterisation methodology is implemented and so, for this reason, the EDAP grade for each one of the following EDAP Maturity matrix items is *'Not Assessable'*:

- **'Uncertainty Characterisation Method'**
- **'Uncertainty Sources Included'**
- **'Uncertainty Values Provided'**

Regarding the last item of Uncertainty Characterisation group, the BlackSky product geolocation uncertainty is described according to these two following ways:

- A single uncertainty value provided for whole mission (whatever the satellite involved in the constellation), as mentioned in [RD 3],
- An uncertainty value provided for each product and report with the parameter "estimatedCE90".

It should have been interested to report on the uncertainty associated to supporting data; raster reference and terrain elevation data. However, residual as the uncertainty is given per product, and it might be a posteriori correlated with other variables (scene location), the EDAP grade for **Geolocation Uncertainty** is *'Intermediate'*.

It is worth noting that the cloud score accuracy is +/- 10 (90 %) as detailed in [RD-3]. As methodology to compute this value is not clearly explained, this information has not been assessed by EDAP.

4.5 Validation

The EDAP validation methodology assesses the consistency between both the BlackSky data values and their uncertainties with those of independent reference data. With respect to the input mission / input data sample characteristics, the validation relied on reference data for the image quality assessment and for the geolocation accuracy assessment. Within this scope, the reference measurements, used for the assessment of other missions, covers a limited range of satellite measurements and their use can be understood as a one-off campaign. For these latter reasons, the EDAP grade for **Reference Data Representativeness** is *'Basic'*. A discussion on reference data is proposed in *section 5*.

The uncertainty of the EDAP reference data is documented through specification documents and publications. The following reference data is used:

- *SPOT 5, Pleiades HR Level 1C products delivered by Airbus DS*
- *ALOS PRISM Level 1C products delivered by ESA (Cat one project)*
- *Ground Control Point Set collected in the test field with GPS device by using a photogrammetric methodology.*
- *Landsat 8 / OLI Top Of Atmosphere data delivered by USGS.*

The uncertainty information is available for anyone of dataset listed above. However, the uncertainty has been assessed by following the GUM approach. For these reasons, the EDAP grade for **Reference Data Quality** is *'Intermediate'*.

As shown within this document, the EDAP validation methodology assess the satellite measurements and reference with regards to reference data. Also, the EDAP grade for **Validation Method** is *'Good'*. For any further information regarding methodology, the following documentation is available:

- The absolute geolocation accuracy is validated using GCPs set derived from GPS test field survey. This survey data has been used for Cal / Val of ALOS PRISM (please refer to [RD-9]).
- The other geometric assessments, referring especially to the internal image accuracy, are performed using image matching techniques implemented by the CNES MEDICIS tool [RD-11].
- The image quality assessment for SNR uses a validated method that is documented presented at the JACIE Workshop [RD-7].
- The image quality assessment for MTF uses a method is described in [RD-8].

The validation results reported herein show some agreement between satellite and reference measurement and therefore the EDAP grade for **Validation Results** is *'Basic'*.

5. DETAILED BLACKSKY QUALITY ASSESSMENT

5.1 Goals

Considering the innovative and often challenging technology associated with Very High Resolution (**VHR**) and High Resolution (**HR**) data, this TN includes assessments regarding geometric calibration and image quality aspects.

5.2 Mission Description and Product Documentation

The BlackSky imagery product specification document [RD-3] is unavailable for public use (i.e. it is only available upon request for data users under a confidential agreement).

In comparison, the ESA Sentinel-2 documentation is broader and comprehends several aspects of the mission. In this section, a comparison of the BlackSky user guide documentation and the Sentinel-2 user guide documentation is provided. Documents and / or any information available for Sentinel-2 not listed in this section can be considered unavailable for BlackSky products.

Mission overview

BlackSky provides an initial section with a product overview and note that, as the mission evolves, this specification document may be superseded by a later version.

Parameter	Value			
Satellite name	Global-01	Global-02	Global-03	Global-04
Operational altitude (apogee)	498 km	590 km	459 km	546 km
Operational altitude (perigee)	472 km	572 km	447 km	540 km
Inclination	97.5° (Sun-sync)	97.7° (Sun-sync)	45.0	45.0
Average sensor-level ground sample distance* at nadir	1.0 m [†]	1.3 m	0.97 m	1.2 m
Image dimensions at minimum coverage [‡]	4.0 km x 6.0 km	4.9 km x 7.3 km	4.0 km x 6.0 km	4.6 km x 7.0 km
Default minimum satellite elevation angle for imaging	60°			
Default minimum solar elevation angle for imaging	10°			
Sensor type [§]	Framing camera with color filter array			
Spectral bands** (nm)	Red	Green	Blue	Panchromatic
	590 - 700	500 - 590	450 - 520	450 - 700

Figure 5-1: Example of BlackSky document table. Mission overview

The Sentinel User Guide is a comprehensive overview of the Sentinel-2 mission in comparison to the BlackSky, including detailed descriptions of heritage missions & usage. The table contains more parameters compared to BlackSky products.

The satellites are not flying in the same way depending on the launch date: the orbital inclination is different, allowing to cover specific countries and address specific markets, as illustrated in the figure hereafter.

Figure 5-2: BlackSky, orbit of the four satellites

The different orbits tell that the flying direction is changing depending on the image. Global-01 and 02 are in a more classic inclination, the along-track direction is approximately associated to the North / South direction, in the case of Global-03 and 04, the inclination is 45 degrees and the direction is West / East.

Sensor Overview

The spacecraft is equipped with a SV-24 (SpaceView 24™) imaging telescope, built by the Harris Corporation, allowing it to image an area approximately 30 km² at high resolution.

Harris SpaceView™ payloads provide high-resolution imagery in a small, lightweight form factor [RD-4]. With apertures ranging from 0.24 m to 0.7 m, SpaceView™ systems meet imaging and size, weight and power requirements for nanosats, microsats, and smallsats with high-resolution imaging ranging from 0.24 m – 1.1 m GSD (Ground Sample Distance). SpaceView™ models 24, 36, and 42 are high-resolution payloads that even offer the potential to capitalize on standard ESPA (Evolved Expendable Launch Vehicle (**EELV**) Secondary Payload Adapter (**ESPA**)) Auxiliary Payload (**APL**) envelope configurations. The SpaceView 24™ imaging telescope parameters are:

- Aperture: 24 cm diameter
- Payload mass: < 10 kg
- Resolution (GSD at 500km): 0.9-1.1 m
- Sensor capabilities: • Staring, • Motion, Imagery/ Video, • Low Light
- Bands: Visible Pan / Colour

The sensor captures imagery using a two-dimensional framing camera with a Bayer Colour Filter Array (**CFA**), as used in the Planet Dove mission.

Products Format / Processing Level

The BlackSky products are delivered in two different product formats, the GeoTIFF format and the National Imagery Transmission Format (**NITF**). In both formats, two processing levels are available: Level 1B and Level 1C.

- The L1B format embeds enhanced images expressed within an instrument grid. The images are fit for visual inspection purposes. The L1B product includes georeferencing information allowing users to perform orthorectification processing by using their own terrain elevation data.
- The L1C format embeds orthorectified image with processing by using raster reference. The important point is that there is no radiometric calibration applied to BlackSky images. The comparison with Sentinel 2 data is not straightforward.

In the BlackSky product description document, there are basic characteristics of each BlackSky product types listed and explained. For Sentinel-2, a separate document for the Product specification is provided which encompasses all the aspects of the product, from product definitions to a full detailed description of each Product Data Item (**PDI**). The fields present in each BlackSky product were compared to the Product specification document and they resulted compliant to the specifications. However, in contrast to the Sentinel-2 documentation, the relevant fields are not present for the BlackSky product metadata.

BlackSky includes their Usable Data Mask image (UDM) in their products. This additional layer has the function of a quality band and gives information regarding clouds, shadows, snow and other field of view obstruction elements (e.g. haze). Although there is a chapter within the product specification documentation for the UDM product and cloud score, detail is missing that would enable users to correlate UDM product raster values with their corresponding data anomalies.

Product processing

The product description document provided by BlackSky includes a section relative to the processing chain, depicted in Figure 5-3. The section is mainly composed of a graph that summarises the processing steps performed and the differences between the product processing levels. The level of detail of this section provides a brief overview for users about the processing blocks (e.g. correction for sensor artefacts, geometric corrections) expected for each product type but does not reach the completeness of an Algorithm Theoretical Baseline Document (**ATBD**) which is distributed for Sentinel-2 products.

A summary of the three levels of BlackSky processing is given below:

- Proto processing reduces sensor-to-sensor variation and corrects for sensor defects or artefacts, improves geolocation accuracy of the image, and assesses the cloud score of the image.
- “Anthro” processing enhances image interpretability to the human eye, adjusts the images colour balance and enhances the images contrast through a dynamic range adjustment.
- Ortho processing prepares the image for viewing on a map by projecting the image into the Universal Transverse Mercator (**UTM**) coordinate system. It removes distortions from perspective, elevation, and sensor optics.

Figure 5-3: BlackSky product processing chain

Geolocation Accuracy

The BlackSky product specification document details the specific steps for improving geolocation accuracy and the processing steps for products. The geolocation processing methodology is provided as a factor of the variability of operational altitudes and angles of the satellites creating differing accuracy from collection to collection that require further geometric processing.

5.3 Product Format Evaluation

5.3.1 Naming conventions and tree structure

An example of product structure sent by the data provider is reported in Table 5-1. The products are bundled by product type. The key parameters are given in the item name, with the following definition:

- BSG-103 is the sensor identifier
- 20191005-123447 is the acquisition date/time (yyyymmdd-hhmmss)
- 465075 is the image identifier

Table 5-1: Product directory organisation

Item	Description
BSG-103-20191005-123447-465075-Tiff	Multi Band GeoTIFF Images (B, G, R, Alpha), Geocoded into Geographic projection
<B_BLUE>	Directory for Blue band GeoTIFF Image, Ortho Rectified (1.0 m), UTM Cartographic Projection
<B_GREEN>	Directory for Green band GeoTIFF Image, Ortho Rectified (1.0 m), UTM Cartographic Projection
<B_RED>	Directory for Red band GeoTIFF Image, Ortho Rectified (1.0 m), UTM Cartographic Projection
<BSG-103-20191005-123447-465075-nitf-non-ortho>	Directory for images (MS / PAN) with no cartographic projection, NITF Format
<BSG-103-20191005-123447-465075-nitf-ortho>	Directory for images (MS / PAN) with cartographic projection, NITF Format
<BSG-103-20191005-123447-465075-non-ortho>	Directory for images (MS / PAN) with no cartographic projection, TIF Format
<BSG-103-20191005-123447-465075-ortho>	Directory for images (MS / PAN) with cartographic projection, TIF Format

The product directories highlighted in blue are the four image product bundles as detailed in the BlackSky product specification document [RD-3] and reported in Table 5-2.

Table 5-2: Files contained in image product bundles

Name	Description	Non-ortho GeoTIFF	Ortho GeoTIFF	Non-ortho NITF	Ortho NITF
RGB image	Natural color image product	✓	✓	✓	✓
Pan image	Panchromatic image product	✓	✓	✓	✓
Browse image	Downsampled PNG of the image for quick browsing of image	✓	✓	✓	✓
Mask file	A GeoTIFF that flags pixels if they are cloudy, saturated, defective, or dead	✓	✗	✓	✗
RPC file	A text file that contains the rational polynomials coefficients for the non-ortho image	✓	✗	✗	✗
Metadata file	A JSON file that contains additional information about the image and its collection	✓	✓	✓	✓
License file	PDF of the end-user license agreement governing the product	✓	✓	✓	✓

The following has been noted about the BlackSky product bundle:

- The browse image is the same whatever the bundle, in particular ortho / non-ortho even if the image is different;
- The metadata file is the same whatever the bundle, also information applicable for the non-ortho product is not applicable for ortho product;
- The Mask file is not available within ortho product bundle, customers are mostly interested in using both ortho image and mask information together.

An example of JSON metadata file included in the non-ortho product bundle is shown below and information that is expected to vary between product types, is highlighted in red. The "registrationPoints" related information might be valid if these points are used to refine the RPC model as included into the "non-ortho" product bundle. Note the accuracy assessment performed here does not confirm this hypothesis.

```
{
  "id" : "BSG-103-20191005-123447-465075",
  "acquisitionDate" : "2019-10-05T12:34:47.500",
  "sensorName" : "Global-3",
  "gsd" : 1.0107892,
```

```
"geometry" : {
  "type" : "Polygon",
  "coordinates" : [ [ [ 5.097818839376503, 43.6397302810637 ], [
5.148137009318115, 43.633722604019894 ], [ 5.133698036587927,
43.577944746936126 ], [ 5.083379866646315, 43.58395242397994 ], [
5.097818839376503, 43.6397302810637 ] ] ]
},
"cloudCoverPercent" : 0.0,
"offNadirAngle" : 10.785954,
"sunElevation" : 39.36286,
"sunAzimuth" : 201.741,
"satelliteElevation" : 76.766136,
"satelliteAzimuth" : 41.283833,
"georeferenced" : true,
"orthorectified" : true,
"width" : 5083,
"height" : 6786,
"processingVersion" : "master-c0a713b82",
"targetType" : "platform_orders",
"estimatedCE90" : 13.389308,
"bitsPerPixel" : 12,
"imageSpecVersion" : "1.0.0",
"fractionSaturated" : 8.953168E-7,
"numberRegistrationPoints" : 30,
"registrationPoints" : [ [ [ 1070.0, 3860.0 ], [ 43.629721949066,
5.098344518344665, 120.08045288935962 ] ], [ [ 5315.0, 3650.0 ], [
43.591232469478435, 5.090874322922562, 109.64312381024999 ] ], [ [
4505.0, 3440.0 ], [ 43.59817277631845, 5.095388984682898,
108.59965514157082 ] ], [ [ 3245.0, 3365.0 ], [ 43.609449015506236,
5.099126267670191, 110.87101943514443 ] ], [ [ 1685.0, 3365.0 ], [
43.623559463351114, 5.102963863096825, 116.75269326109691 ] ], [ [
2555.0, 3185.0 ], [ 43.615454392787264, 5.1030530475860285,
112.02134550289954 ] ], [ [ 5225.0, 3065.0 ], [ 43.59123129244467,
5.098306902426756, 106.60851465992299 ] ], [ [ 3620.0, 2930.0 ], [
43.60544946360255, 5.103633608118523, 108.96906770116921 ] ], [ [
4160.0, 2675.0 ], [ 43.60014797540183, 5.105493080813695,
107.17052032750553 ] ], [ [ 5405.0, 2525.0 ], [ 43.58882067765107,
```

```

5.104540594959507, 113.0 ] ], [ [ 1025.0, 2480.0 ], [
43.62806049628494, 5.1152062343818905, 118.0177866257788 ] ], [ [
6005.0, 2225.0 ], [ 43.582972442573755, 5.106752040756781,
128.6146934488199 ] ], [ [ 4850.0, 2105.0 ], [ 43.593158259806806,
5.111009735670798, 112.36973530452038 ] ], [ [ 455.0, 2090.0 ], [
43.63267418186392, 5.121318295597495, 136.2541094202282 ] ], [ [
4205.0, 1970.0 ], [ 43.59877207863836, 5.114179498053831,
107.56005816347012 ] ], [ [ 5450.0, 1805.0 ], [ 43.58730991322658,
5.113220692530621, 121.0911313819872 ] ], [ [ 980.0, 1760.0 ], [
43.62748669265484, 5.124296535127129, 122.9296960280453 ] ], [ [
1850.0, 1430.0 ], [ 43.619212146937336, 5.126235881310538,
121.31355571920606 ] ], [ [ 4445.0, 1355.0 ], [ 43.595671963826014,
5.121132415111974, 117.00000000000003 ] ], [ [ 6125.0, 1160.0 ], [
43.58030263711222, 5.1196636269814055, 147.6100699250541 ] ], [ [
1670.0, 1040.0 ], [ 43.62019498046092, 5.131475860670073,
124.31309841225914 ] ], [ [ 260.0, 1010.0 ], [ 43.63282297768862,
5.135083357119399, 139.2766095207059 ] ], [ [ 2405.0, 965.0 ], [
43.61345696663689, 5.1306801095640155, 118.90695433168389 ] ], [ [
680.0, 785.0 ], [ 43.62873922206682, 5.1367980412970935,
126.92239888112648 ] ], [ [ 3815.0, 770.0 ], [ 43.60050692009147,
5.129851161321846, 127.86381772258477 ] ], [ [ 4895.0, 590.0 ], [
43.59051923033653, 5.129498770764454, 156.6980670626637 ] ], [ [
1760.0, 560.0 ], [ 43.618737730817, 5.137187261498034, 123.0 ] ],
[ [ 5630.0, 395.0 ], [ 43.58361850947806, 5.13018436153758,
139.54820803724917 ] ], [ [ 545.0, 395.0 ], [ 43.62932013126121,
5.141838813187506, 128.00000000000003 ] ], [ [ 3530.0, 35.0 ], [
43.602081091447985, 5.1395708511391005, 165.50807078723858 ] ] ],

  "gemini" : {

    "catalogImageId" : "63304",

    "imageId" : "465075"

  }

}

```

In addition, the ground sample distance related to the raw imagery varies depending on the viewing angle. This information is reported as part of the metadata file information. Also, depending on images and observation geometries, the value of GSD JSON parameter varies. Nonetheless, the pixel spacing, 1.0 m, of the ortho images is not indicated. Note that depending on the BlackSky satellite involved, the average pixel spacing at Nadir changes from 0.97 m (Global-03) to 1.2 m (Global-04).

5.3.2 Metadata content

The metadata are contained within a single JSON file, an example of which is given above.

From a data quality point of view, there are several interesting features, as discussed in [RD-3]:

- "estimatedCE90": Geolocation accuracy of the image, computed against the raster reference using independent check point,
- "fractionSaturated": Quality indicator of saturated / cloudy pixels,

- "numberRegistrationPoints" / "registrationPoints": Details on GCP involved in the calibration of the geometric model, allowing to assess the spatial distribution of the GCP set.

It is worth noting that the distinction between GCPs, involved in the geometric model calibration and independent check point, is not proposed.

5.3.3 Usable Data Mask format

On the form of a quality assessment mask, there is UDM. The UDM is an 8-bit quality image that provides a description of the quality of the pixels within a scene. The bit-packed information in the QA mask is a translation of binary strings. The definition of the UDM, provided by BlackSky is given in Table 5-3. BlackSky uses a proprietary cloud detection algorithm to flag each pixel as cloudy or not cloudy. Furthermore, accurate geometrically located cloud pixels are unlikely because the cloud detection is run on an image down-sampled by a factor of 30.

For instance, if a pixel is saturated, a test of the pixel bit sequence with the following bit mask "0b0000100" will return "True".

Table 5-3: The definition of the usable data mask

Bit	7	6	5	4	3	2	1	0
Description	unused	transparent	reserved	cloud	cloud	saturated	defective	dead

One limitation for the users of the ortho product is that the UDM is only embedded in the non-ortho product bundle. As for any data in this bundle, the quality image should be geometrically processed by using the proposed RPC.

The definition of the UDM is not well documented. Quality information associated with each mask is in most cases relevant and correct. Transparent / reserved bits (bits 6 and 5, respectively) are never used.

Images of the UDM are shown in Figure 5-4 with the five main classes illustrated. When zooming in on the left part of the image, the roof of the houses and greenhouse are tagged as saturated and cloudy.

"Cloud2" is actually a dilatation (image morphological operation) of the "Cloud" mask. In a similar way, the distinction between defective and dead pixels is not totally clear. This figure confirms that shadows and thin clouds are not detected. BlackSky specification clearly states that haze is not detected.

Figure 5-4: UDM Mask, BSG-102-20191024-104036-525146. Top image, without cloud mask, middle image and bottom un-zoomed image with cloud mask

The inspection of the UDM is reported in the following sections of this document. All UDMs in the delivered dataset have been checked and visually inspected.

5.3.4 Image format

The image data are either formatted according to the TIFF v1.0 specification (GeoTiff format) or according to the NITF 2.1 (US Defence format).

The compression algorithm used for the GeoTiff format is 'DEFLATE' and the compression algorithms used for the NITF is JPG 2000. For standard non-ortho / ortho products, the 12-bit dynamic range is coded over 2 bytes (16 bits). The NITF format as proposed by BlackSky is optimised for cloud environment (Cloud Optimized GeoTiff).

It is not straightforward to compare performance of the compression based on file size because GeoTiff format includes an additional mask layer while the NITF format does not. Regarding NITF, the compression scheme (optimised / regular) for the JPEG 2000 is not, however, documented.

In the case of one ortho product (BSG-103 -20191005), the size of the image file is following ones depending on the format. It shows that with the NITF format, the file size is significantly reduced:

- Panchromatic band: 68 MB (TIFF) / 39.5 MB (NITF)
- RGB band: 179.4 MB (TIFF) / 77.9 MB (NITF).

Note that, the Standard Open-Source Geospatial library ingests NITF image format and can convert it to GeoTIFF format.

5.3.5 Georeferencing

GeoTIFF Tags / NITF Tags embedded in the product format allow georeferencing of the products. An example of TIFF tags available in the orthorectified image is given below.

```
Image Width: 5083 Image Length: 6786  
  
Bits/Sample: 16  
  
Compression Scheme: AdobeDeflate  
  
Photometric Interpretation: min-is-black  
  
Extra Samples: 1<assoc-alpha>  
  
FillOrder: msb-to-lsb  
  
Orientation: row 0 top, col 0 lhs  
  
Samples/Pixel: 2  
  
Rows/Strip: 16  
  
Planar Configuration: single image plane
```

```

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98109

Tag 33550: 1.000000,1.000000,0.000000

Tag 33922:
0.000000,0.000000,0.000000,668194.000005,4834000.999728,0.000000

Tag 34735:
1,1,0,4,1024,0,1,1,1025,0,1,1,3072,0,1,32631,3073,34737,22,0

Tag 34737: WGS 84 / UTM zone 31N|
  
```

For non-ortho products, coarse georeferencing is possible by using the GeoTIFF Tags. There are also the GeoTIFF Tags dedicated to accurate georeferencing based on RPC coefficients particularly well suited for narrow field of view sensor. This information is replicated and written into a dedicated ASCII file. It is therefore possible to use the RPC coefficient for georeferencing purposes.

By adding auxiliary information, such as digital elevation data and a set of ground control points, a warping process should allow for the creation of an accurate ortho product starting from the non-ortho product.

5.4 Image Quality and Interpretability

5.4.1 Activity description sheet

Visual inspection
<i>Inputs</i>
Set of Level 1 BlackSky data observed over Salon-de-Provence (France). The non-ortho GeoTIFF processing level is selected because the UDM is only provided for products from this processing level. This processing level requires geometric pre-processing by using RPC set and DEM data.
<i>Description</i>
Check image quick look generated from the input products Check colour composite of full resolution images Check content of the mask included in the standard products
<i>Outputs</i>
Qualitative assessment of the image data information, included quality assurance information.

5.4.2 Introduction

The BlackSky constellation provides 1.0 m GSD VHR Multispectral and Panchromatic imagery. The imagery is always accompanied with a UDM. The “anthro” processing, discussed previously (see section 5.2), is intended to improve the quality of an image solely dedicated to object recognition. A major drawback of the “anthro” processing approach is that there is no relationship between DN values and physical measurements (TOA

reflectances). It is therefore understood that the data quality should be analysed from the perspective of a data analyst operator in charge of identifying objects.

According to the National Imagery Interpretability Rating Scale (NIIRS)⁵ rating the quality of spatial / aerial imagery, a scale of 5 (out of 9) can be applied to BlackSky. With a rating of 5, it is possible to identify tents at a camping site and detect large animals in grasslands. BlackSky data is equivalent to Pleiades multispectral data, in the way that a same object detected in Pleiades data can be detected, recognised and identified in BlackSky data.

Two fundamental aspects of the product have been addressed with this work: the UDM mask (section 5.4.3) and the image interpretability (section 5.4.4).

5.4.3 Usable Data Mask

As discussed previously, the BlackSky non-ortho products include a quality assurance mask. The consistency / correctness of this information has been checked (section 5.3.3) with the two following approaches:

1. Extract statistics from the quality assurance mask;
2. Visual inspection of the mask for each item.

5.4.3.1 Quality assurance mask statistics

The 8-bit mask has been extracted from all products in the delivered dataset. There are two groups of indicators; a first group dealing with the instrument quality state (dead detector, defective detector) and a second group concerning parameters derived directly from the scene (saturation, cloud). Concerning our assessment method, a quality control process has been developed to count saturated pixels and compare with results in the mask.

Note that for correct geometric registration between the image and mask, the orthorectification process, by using the RPCs, should be applied. Note also, that there are two cloud masks giving two cloud scores; “Cloud 1” & “Cloud 2”.

Table 5-4 shows statistical results for all investigated products. Several observations can be formulated:

- The number of dead / defective pixels number is stable and depends on the mission, the quality state of Global-01 / Global-02 is degraded compared to the two other missions. Note that statistics are different because the image geometry is “projected”;
- “Cloud 1” is always bigger than “Cloud 2” because of image processing with morphological operator (dilatation);
- The Cloud score report in the metadata file is in agreement with results given with ‘Cloud 2’;
- A metadata parameter, named “Fraction of saturated” is not in agreement with statistical values found (with our method);
 - The number of saturated pixels (computed based on panchromatic image) does not necessarily depend on the mission, but more on the acquisition geometries.

⁵ <https://fas.org/irp/imint/niirs.htm>

Global-03 & Global-04 images might be more subject to data saturation due to orbit.

Table 5-4: UDM Mask check results

Product Id	Site	QA_Mask dead	QA_Mask defective	QA_Mask saturated	QA_Mask cloud1	QA_Mask cloud2	Total size	Valid Value	Saturated px (>4096)	json cloud score	json fraction saturated	cloud2 /val_px
BSG-101-20191015-102859-499986	La Crau	261310	59667	15102	46629	16666	49419760	37066007	0	0.06	1.24E-05	0.03
BSG-102-20191024-104036-525146	La Crau	399554	113907	15329	2049586	1463081	63742448	46870269	0	2.77	0	3.12
BSG-103-20191005-105550-464915	La Crau	70543	56708	18464	0	0	55975336	37306415	0	0.00	0	0.00
BSG-103-20191011-085000-484115	La Crau	57131	46091	12887	1253052	921494	35956224	30210700	0	2.77	0	3.05
BSG-104-20191025-094224-528654	La Crau	48936	62136	14964	13942	1812	53829152	41929186	0	0.00	0	0.00
BSG-104-20191029-091006-539183	La Crau	54124	68616	11885	400187	252855	50660224	46355224	0	0.53	0	0.55
BSG-103-20191005-123447-465075	Salon	49176	39641	8961	0	0	34516980	25969669	18981	0.00	0.00	0.00
BSG-103-20191011-085019-484116	Salon	61058	49180	13951	4673680	3923138	34346604	32243987	4857	12.83	0.00	12.17
BSG-103-20191014-083533-496003	Salon	60895	49197	8395	1056621	827523	36144801	32192084	3580	2.62	0.00	2.57
BSG-101-20191008-101145-472729	Piedmont	222713	51932	10049	649440	404573	37733088	31709664	1928	1.15	0	1.28
BSG-102-20191005-103538-464692	Piedmont	460149	129399	35866	32067470	26106269	78377376	54079732	14981	42.75	0	48.27
BSG-103-20191005-105633-464916	Piedmont	53418	42241	12664	649248	367395	37120575	28649084	22671	1.33	0	1.28
BSG-101-20191007-090602-470173	Libya	217801	49772	4613	57261	1490	39612482	30530417	3607	0.01	0	0.00
BSG-101-20191007-090602-470173	Libya	266621	61243	4489	33744	310	42998568	37365218	5155	0.01	0	0.00
BSG-102-20191005-090352-464670	Libya	338940	97124	24785	277	58	50424192	39355170	61083	0.00	0	0.00

5.4.3.2 Mask visual inspection

The visual inspection confirms statistical results discussed previously. Furthermore, additional work has been performed to check consistency / fidelity of the mask, for dead / defective detectors and saturated / cloudy pixel values.

As a general remark, the UDM mask is perfectly registered to the image data. Inconsistent image pixels due to dead detectors are systematically observed in all image bands at the same location. The use of one mask is sufficient.

As shown in Figure 5-5, some inconsistent pixel values due to dead / defective detectors that are not flagged.

BSG-103-20191005-123447-
 465075_defective (Salon), blue
 band image.

Figure 5-5: Inconsistencies in the “Dead” pixel mask

Moreover, as shown in Figure 5-6, correctly flagged “Dead detector” pixels can recover its nominal behaviour (flying direction from West to East).

Figure 5-6: “Dead” pixel set becomes operational

The “defective” pixels set has been assessed. The meaning of this flagging is not clear, however, in most cases, these pixels are appropriate for analysis. Comparing two observations, as shown in Figure 5-7, the mask is static, it depends on the mission and does not depend on the observation date. Furthermore, the figure shows rounded patterns flagging concerned pixels, the origin of this pattern form is unclear.

BSG-103-20191005-105550-
 464915_defective (La Crau),
 blue band image.

BSG-103-20191005-123447-
 465075_defective (Salon), blue
 band image.

Figure 5-7: “Defective” pixel set does not change depending on the observation date (BSG-103)

As mentioned previously, the cloud cover is calculated using a Deep Learning architecture. BlackSky specifies that > 90% of its products have a cloud score with +/- 10 of truth. This assertion is difficult to verify. The cloud mask associated with the sample dataset for this study, has been checked and it can be confirmed that the detection is very consistent and rather conservative. The cloud processing algorithm performs well in various conditions as shown in Figure 5-8 and the good quality of the mask can be noted for data observed over mountainous regions. False detection exists, but appears relatively infrequently. Errors were, however, observed over specific desert sites.

Figure 5-8: Cloud Cover detection over (Salon-de-Provence). Left images without cloud mask, right images showing cloud mask. Top: BSG.16, middle: BSG.17, bottom: BSG.18.

BSG-101-20191007-090630-470174

Figure 5-9: Cloud Cover detection, bright source (Libya-4 BSG.11).

BSG-102-20191005-103538-464692_cloud2

Figure 5-10: Cloud Cover detection, haze in mountain (Piedmont BSG.13).

Regarding image saturation, due to post processing, the definition of saturated pixels is not straightforward: defining a maximum DN limit at 4096 is not relevant because image processing extends the image histogram to 16-bit value, at the risk of quantification issue as shown. Image saturation is more frequently observed in the panchromatic band. The mask does not indicate which band is contaminated. According to the mask, the saturation is not observed over cloud, but rather over building roofs.

5.4.3.3 Summary

The main findings and limitations as a result of our inspection are:

- Cloud detection performs well with some limitations for haze / cirrus and some limitations over specific sites;
- Misclassifications are observed but, in most cases, this information is reliable;
- The flagging always concerns all the bands: any issue affecting only one spectral band image is reported as affecting all bands;
- Calibration table regarding dead / defective detector should be more routinely maintained;
- The definition of data saturation is actually scene dependant because of histogram equalisation process;
- The designated pixel is not implemented and as a consequence, image background cannot be flagged (refer to Landsat QA Mask [RD-6]);
- The shadow is not flagged, which is of great interest for VHR data.

5.4.4 Image Interpretability

As mentioned in the introduction, the image interpretability is a critical aspect of VHR data: 1.0 m GSD data should support an analyst in detecting, recognising and identifying objects.

A main input to this assessment is the definition of objects (object database) and the access to reference data for visual comparison of objects seen with two different sensors of the same NIIRS scale.

Besides the above, we are interested in the assessment of the “anthro” processing and its impact on image quality. We are also interested in the image quality depending on the spectral channels and depending on the missions.

5.4.4.1 Methods

The object database relies on POIs selected for their characteristics: manmade objects / natural objects. Within the delivered dataset, data observed over Salon-de-Provence and dated of October 5 2019 has been selected, “BSG-103-20191005-123447-465075 non-ortho” (BSG.16). Figure 5-11 shows the distribution of POIs over the corresponding Green Band image.

Figure 5-11: Point of Interest (POI) over BlackSky Green Band image observed over Salon (BSG-103-20191005-123447-465075 non-ortho – BSG.16).

The method consists of clipping input images (all BlackSky channels) within a 400 x 400 pixels window centred on the POI. The full resolution images displayed on screen are checked and compared to Pléiades reference data (side-by-side). From a radiometric point of view, there is no post processing applied to BlackSky data (e.g. processing such as equalisation, stretching, etc.).

The extraction of image data is performed together with the computation of a histogram associated with the POI image subset.

This procedure is also repeated with Pléiades High Resolution (**PHR**) data. The PHR data is Multispectral data (2.0 m), resampled to 1.0 m by using cubic convolution. The data from Panchromatic band (0.7 m) is not part of the product delivered by Airbus.

Table 5-5 below lists the POIs used in this assessment, a short description of each is given.

Table 5-5: POI over the Salon-d-Provence scene

wkgt_geom (UTM 31)	Id	Description
Point (671090.3105554151115939 4830278.58671295549720526)	1	Modulation Transfer Function target
Point (671364.24309313111007214 4833044.0252351425588131)	2	Motor way / sharp transition (45° NE)
Point (668580.81736886233557016 4828965.45189037173986435)	3	Forest
Point (670056.62237295764498413 4828905.08180973120033741)	4	Roundabout / parking lot
Point (669985.90922565956134349 4832120.72269264236092567)	5	Elevated tree
Point (669956.03863696497865021 4832655.53592716064304113)	6	Motor way / roundabout
Point (670564.24590074480511248 4833363.40447467099875212)	7	The dam
Point (669836.88448120269458741 4832528.00618595350533724)	8	Big building (shadow)
Point (670518.95015854423400015 4829513.56928175128996372)	9	Landing track - 34
Point (670249.72702971810940653 4831735.0312919020652771)	10	Floor Painting
Point (670900.38168655894696712 4829617.21182315889745951)	11	Crop fields / sparse
Point (671548.0352310094749555 4830292.1131860688328743)	12	Broadleaved woodland
Point (671099.93821095407474786 4828090.14610077627003193)	13	Crop fields
Point (671156.44116920174565166 4828825.77096180152148008)	14	Bridge and water
Point (671120.4438803291413933 4827691.31545618735253811)	15	Crop fields
Point (670328.31568091106601059 4831489.30539688002318144)	16	Building / EA 15
Point (671516.86161747551523149 4833207.41657157335430384)	17	Greenhouse

wkgt_geom (UTM 31)	Id	Description
Point (669996.87127304612658918 4829099.09009433817118406)	18	Parking lot
Point (670062.87681329366751015 4829781.35287734866142273)	19	Plane parking
Point (670860.46870227111503482 4831527.10888031311333179)	20	Plane hangar
Point (671802.47347140731289983 4832385.40385554917156696)	21	Small crop fields
Point (671246.59432400949299335 4832300.03732818737626076)	22	Urban city

5.4.4.2 Results

As shown in Figure 5-12 and Figure 5-13 below, depending on the observation geometry, the quality of the mission and the “adaptive” image processing applied, the quality of the image varies greatly.

Figure 5-12: Comparison between four panchromatic images from different satellites, Global-01 / Global-03 / Global-04. La Crau site, scale: 1:10000.

Figure 5-13: Comparison between four panchromatic full resolution images from different satellites, Global-01 / Global-03 / Global-04. La Crau site, scale: 1:2620 (full resolution).

The full visual inspection analysis, including the BlackSky / PHR comparisons for all bands in all provided products, is presented in [RD-5]. A few examples of the full resolution comparisons, and the associated conclusions are shown in Figure 5-14 to Figure 5-20 below.

Figure 5-15 shows that despite the coarse PHR MS image spatial resolution (2.0 m), finer details over uniform regions can be better distinguished compared to the corresponding BlackSky image (Figure 5-14). For example, note the differences in the white lane nearby the roundabout in the left part of the image, or sparse objects (trees) over uniform background in the lower part. In addition, the inner part of the soccer field is better detailed in the PHR image. This may be due to the spectral definition or more practically due to change of the terrain properties between the two PHR/BSG observation dates. The location of these differences is indicated with an arrow.

Figure 5-14: Image Interpretability – Full resolution BSG Image (Red) of POI (Id 14).

Figure 5-15: Image Interpretability – Full resolution PHR Image (Red) of POI (Id 14).

In Figure 5-16, the image texture in the fields has been lost in the BlackSky image compared to PHR (Figure 5-17).

Figure 5-16: Image Interpretability – Full resolution BSG Image (Red) of POI (Id 15).

Figure 5-17: Image Interpretability – Full resolution PHR Image (Red) of POI (Id 15).

It is much easier to distinguish the four roofs in the BlackSky image in Figure 5-18 than the PHR equivalent (Figure 5-19). Conversely, details in the tarmac are less visible in the BlackSky image and the road at the end of the track (upper arrow) is missing.

Figure 5-18: Image Interpretability – Full resolution BSG Image (Green) of POI (Id 19).

Figure 5-19: Image Interpretability – Full resolution PHR Image (Green) of POI (Id 15).

Figure 5-20: Image Interpretability – Aerial Photo (Object Id 15) – note road at the end of the track.

5.4.4.3 Summary

The quality of BlackSky images differs depending on the bands. More noise is observed in the red band and a panchromatic image that cannot be used as is.

The histogram equalisation / sharpening applied is efficient and removes most of the noise, at the risk of removing texture over uniform areas. The post processing algorithms tend to remove details in the low / high part of the dynamic range.

BlackSky is equivalent to PHR (2.0 m rescaled to 1.0 m) and in most cases better. It is however interesting that in some specific configurations Pleiades performs better.

5.5 Geometric Calibration / Validation

5.5.1 Activity Description Sheet

Geometric Accuracy Validation: Absolute / Multitemporal / Interband registration
<i>Inputs</i>
<p>Set of Level 1 BlackSky data observed over La Crau / Salon-de-Provence (France) and Piedmont (Italy).</p> <p>As processing input, the products from two processing levels are considered; “non-ortho” (Level 1B) and “ortho” (Level 1C) GeoTIFFs. The “non-ortho” products require geometric pre-processing using RPCs and DEM data.</p>
<i>Description</i>
<p>Estimate the absolute geometric accuracy of input Level 1C products by using two distinct methods:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Semi-automatic identification of GCP set from test field survey • Matching with a raster reference. <p>Estimate the multi-temporal accuracy for a set of observations performed over the same region of interest (Level 1C).</p> <p>Estimate the inter-band registration accuracy (Level 1C).</p> <p>Estimate the absolute accuracy of RPCs delivered with the Level 1B product.</p> <p>As stated in the product specification document [RD-3], the absolute geolocation accuracy should be within 20 m (CE90). Within this latter document, there is no information regarding the other accuracy parameters (e.g. inter-band registration accuracy and multi-temporal geolocation accuracy).</p>
<i>Outputs</i>
<p>All proposed EDAP validation methods show that the absolute accuracy is slightly above the claimed geolocation accuracy. Accuracy results are in the range of 20.0 m to 30.0 m for what concerned test sites located over flat terrain relief. A degraded accuracy is observed for regions displaying hilly terrain relief (Piedmont).</p> <p>The inter-band registration accuracy is below 0.01 pixel (RMSE).</p> <p>The multi temporal accuracy is within 10.0 m (CE90). These results are due to the accuracy of the Digital Elevation Model (DEM) involved in the BlackSky processing. For this spatial resolution it is important to account for over ground features (building).</p> <p>The geometric processing of Level 1B products, by using RPCs and internal DEM data, the EDAP analysis shows that a better precision can be achieved. The</p>

Geometric Accuracy Validation: Absolute / Multitemporal / Interband registration

accuracy of the resulting product remains poor because the RPC set is not calibrated and a static bias of about 30.0 m is always observed.

5.5.2 Introduction

In this section dedicated to the analysis of geometric calibration, EDAP's three classical accuracy assessments are performed; absolute accuracy, multi-temporal accuracy and interband accuracy.

The absolute accuracy cannot be estimated using GCPs alone as the scene footprint of a BlackSky product is relatively small, approximately 4 km (width) x 6 km (height), and so usually no more than five to six GCPs can be used (this number of GCPs is too small to analyse image distortions). Therefore, the latter is complemented by a method based on making comparisons between a BlackSky image grid and a raster reference image grid by using an image matching tool.

The absolute geolocation assessment has been applied to the Red and PAN bands in order to check consistency and compare with interband registration results.

As for the interband analysis, the multi-temporal accuracy assessment uses the same method based on image matching.

Finally, the analysis on product geometry focuses on the accuracy of the RPC generic model defined with the related ancillary data included in the Level 1B (default "non-ortho" product).

5.5.3 Absolute Geolocation Accuracy with GCP

5.5.3.1 Methods

The absolute geometric accuracy considers the Level 1C products (ortho tiles) as input to the analysis. The approach consists of identifying GCPs collected during GPS field surveys in the input image. To increase the number of GCPs included within the image extent, several ortho tiles have been collected and stitched. Data collected in the La Crau site (France) was used.

5.5.3.2 Results

As shown in Figure 5-22, the GCPs geographical distribution covers the full extent of the image, however the low number of GCPs present within the image extents should be noted as the overall statistical reliability of Absolute Geolocation Accuracy results will be poor.

Table 5-6 reports the absolute geolocation accuracy of BlackSky data for the product concerned (BSG.4). The observed bias (mean error) might be introduced by the reference used for the co-registration. It is interesting to note that the precision of measurement exceeds 3.125 m in the two Northing / Easting directions. It reveals GCP point accuracy degradation and / or internal image distortions.

Table 5-6: Absolute Geolocation Accuracy Results (Absolute, in meter unit).

	Absolute geolocation accuracy (metres)
Sample (#GCP)	4
Easting Error Mean (m)	13.61
Northing Error Mean (m)	21.41
Easting Error Std (m)	5.09
Northing Error Std (m)	6.26
Easting Error RMS (m)	25.37
Northing Error RMS (m)	22.31
Root Mean Square Error (m)	33.78
Circular Error @90 Percentile (m)	28.09

Figure 5-21: Geometric Accuracy - Circular Error Plot (La Crau).

Figure 5-22: Geometric Accuracy – Composite Level 3A Tile product with GCPs (La Crau).

5.5.4 Absolute Geolocation Accuracy with Matching

5.5.4.1 Methods

The comparison between the BlackSky geometric grid and the raster reference geometric grid is performed by using a classical image matching approach relying on an intensity-based method (Normalised Cross Correlation (**NCC**)). The advantage of the method is to detect distortions in the images. A disadvantage of this method is the selection of the most confident measurements involved in the accuracy analysis, mostly affected by noise in some cases.

The origin of the raster reference involved in the matching depends on the test site location:

- For Salon-de-Provence and La Crau sites, the same SPOT-5 MS image has been selected and processed.
- For the Piedmont site, an ALOS PRISM image has been selected and processed.

The pixel spacing of these PRISM and SPOT-5 products is 2.5 m, above that of BlackSky (1.0 m). The qualification of our reference data shows that the RMS accuracy of SPOT-5 and PRISM data is below 2.5 m with very good internal geometry. Also, we considered that it is sufficient to check geometry of BlackSky data which are foreseen to have an accuracy above 1.0 m. The interest of using SPOT-5 MS data is also the large geographical extent of the reference image covering both La Crau and Salon-de-Provence sites.

The BlackSky images over these two sites have actually been observed within the same period of time: during observation, the pointing angle of the platform has been tuned to capture images on both sides of the satellite nadir with pointing change in a very short period.

This assertion is illustrated with the following two products; these products have been recorded with a 19 second lag and observed with a pointing angle set in the opposite direction.

- BSG-103-20191011-085000-484115 (La Crau), pointing angle is -18.17°
- BSG-103-20191011-085019-484116 (Salon-de-Provence), pointing angle is 21.5°

This kind of configuration makes the analysis of absolute geolocation very interesting, in particular the check of point stability within a short period of time. Keeping in mind that the raster reference remains the same, with a very stable internal image from a geometric point of view.

As shown in Section 5.5.5, the co-registration between bands is correct, therefore, the use of only one band for this assessment is sufficient. It is the image band with the best quality of information to be matched that was used for this analysis; the RED band.

Furthermore, the procedure might be applied to both product types; the delivered ortho product and the post-processed non-ortho product (RPC). Indeed, RPC coefficient set and digital elevation model can be used for geo coding / orthorectification purposes. Such a procedure is discussed in the part dedicated to multi-temporal accuracy (5.5.6). It has been observed, that when processed by using both RPCs and a finer resolution DEM, the internal geometry of the resulting image is improved compared to the standard ortho product. In particular, the precision is better. However, geolocation quality results exhibits

a large static bias, meaning that RPCs are not calibrated from systematic distortions (a 30.0 m static observed).

For this reason, this part of the report is exclusively focused on the absolute location accuracy of the delivered ortho product.

5.5.4.2 Results

The absolute location results are listed in Table 5-7. Besides accuracy results, the table reports several parameters, such as off-nadir angle and azimuth angle of the instrument; the circular error at 90th percentile and the cloud cover percentage; all information extracted from the product metadata. As part of the accuracy results, the mean accuracy (mean Error), the precision (Std Error), the radial error and computed circular error at 90th percentile, are reported, expressed into meter units.

Considering the Salon-de-Provence and La Crau sites, the absolute location results confirms the large geolocation shift observed in the previous assessment (using GCPs). The mean radial error is below 20.0 m and the circular error is below 28.0 m. The estimated circular error value is twice above the circular error given in the metadata (within 14.0 m). The accuracy does not change depending on the missions, except for BSG-104 which is slightly better.

As shown in the dense matching report figures (Figure 5-23, Figure 5-24, Figure 5-25), the statistical distribution of residual errors is correct in both directions. For some products, the scatter plot exhibits two modes. For BSG.18, this is due to artefacts from the terrain relief: the planimetric accuracy is degraded, the elevation value retained for orthoprocessing is wrong, and consequently, the location of the pixel in the object space is not correct.

It is worth noting that in the initial assessment, the image matching did not work in an optimal way because of image processing applied to remove texture in the image and therefore prevented matching over large / uniform area where information content is usually high and particularly well suited for matching.

Concerning the Piedmont site, due to location of the mountainous site (elevation > 2000 m), including steep relief, the three results are in the same order of magnitude as the other sites. The circular error is within 55.0 m, mainly due to planimetric offset. The internal image is correct and distortions are due to the relief.

Table 5-7: Absolute geolocation accuracy results.

Product Id	EDAP ID	Site	Off nadir Angle (dd)	Estimated CE (mtl)	Cloud Cover %	Sat Az (dd)	Mean Error northing (m) (3)	Mean Error easting (m) (3)	Std Error northing (m)	Std Error easting (m)	Radial Error (m)	CE (m)
BSG-103-20191005-123447-465075	BSG.16	Salon	10.79	13.39	0.00	41	-12.45	14.95	3.48	3.43	19.46	24.12
BSG-103-20191011-085019-484116	BSG.17	Salon	21.56	11.01	12.83	30	-15.13	12.14	4.88	5.07	19.39	26.02
BSG-103-20191014-083533-496003	BSG.18	Salon	-21.60	11.32	2.62	313	-16.15	10.75	3.41	3.81	19.40	23.56
BSG-102-20191005-103538-464692	BSG.13	Piedmont	-22.32	17.42	42.75	289	40.93	-3.66	3.11	9.80	41.09	45.97
BSG-103-20191005-105633-464916	BSG.14	Piedmont	-16.36	13.40	1.33	271	48.24	1.19	3.36	8.01	48.25	52.37
BSG-101-20191008-101145-472729	BSG.15	Piedmont	-16.83	11.80	1.15	98	49.97	2.66	3.63	8.08	50.04	55.25
BSG-101-20191015-102859-499986	BSG.3	La Crau	20.75	12.74	0.06	6	-17.09	8.61	6.63	5.88	19.14	25.44
BSG-102-20191024-104036-525146	BSG.4	La Crau	-19.19	12.71	2.77	260	-11.70	8.63	10.53	11.43	14.54	26.42
BSG-103-20191005-105550-464915	BSG.1	La Crau	-27.23	12.69	0.00	289	-15.48	9.89	5.51	5.74	18.37	24.34
BSG-103-20191011-085000-484115	BSG.2	La Crau	-18.17	12.09	2.77	357	-8.95	14.08	10.52	9.42	16.69	28.12
BSG-104-20191025-094224-528654	BSG.5	La Crau	-14.34	12.05	0.00	340	-13.62	5.36	11.96	11.32	14.64	27.75
BSG-104-20191029-091006-539183	BSG.6	La Crau	-19.98	13.39	0.53	316	-13.03	2.90	11.25	10.73	13.35	25.77

- (1) For Salon-de-Provence / La Crau sites, SPOT-5 data have been used as reference.
- (2) For Piedmont, PRISM data has been used as reference.
- (3) The cartographic error is the difference between position predicted by BlackSky model and position predicted by using the reference data.

Figure 5-23: Dense Matching Report (BSG.16).

Figure 5-24: Dense Matching Report (BSG.17).

Figure 5-25: Dense Matching Report (BSG.18).

5.5.5 Interband Geometric Accuracy

5.5.5.1 Methods

The interband geometric accuracy assessment relies on the following principles:

- Compare geometry between two image bands by using image matching;
- Evaluate geometric registration testing all possible band combinations; including the Blue, Green, Red, and Panchromatic bands;
- Compute error budget and output global statistics.

The Libya 4, La Crau and Wellington sites have been selected as appropriate sites for computing interband registration.

5.5.5.2 Results

Regardless of the site and the mission, the results were almost the same. The overall error of the method is within 0.005 pixel. The registration of the MS bands is within accuracy expectation below 0.01 pixel.

Figure 5-26: Band-to-Band registration, mean accuracy (La Crau).

The results were different for band-to-band registration between the panchromatic band and multispectral bands. Depending on the satellite, large differences can be observed; in particular with BSG-104 where registration accuracy is within 0.25 pixels in both directions. Otherwise for all other missions, the registration between PAN / MS bands is within 0.02 pixels.

5.5.6 Multi-Temporal Geometric Accuracy

This assessment was performed by using the Salon-de-Provence dataset, and includes three products observed with the same spacecraft (BSG-103). Other sites have been used but unfortunately information to be matched was not sufficient for an-depth analysis of accuracy results. It is worth noting that the accuracy results are given for the panchromatic images, these results remain quite close considering multispectral images.

Table 5-8 below lists for the three image twins, the co-registration accuracy results obtained with image matching. The accuracy of geometric co-registration is within 10 m (CE90), which is within the operational goal.

A transitivity check, subtracting accuracy results (mean error in both directions) from the two first twins and comparing with results of the last twin (BSG.17 / BSG.18), shows that confidence is very high.

Co-registration of one image twin (BSG.17 / BSG.18), last column, is very good; the mean accuracy is within 0.2 m and the uncertainty is essentially due to the precision lost (within 2.0 m in both directions).

Co-registration of the two other image twins shows degradation of the mean accuracy: 6.0 m / 3.5 in both Easting and Northing directions, respectively.

The ortho processing of BSG.17 / BSG.18 image grids are particularly subject to distortions because these have been observed from opposing off-nadir angles, respectively 21.56° and -21.60°. Although results are correct.

Finally, the multi temporal accuracy is unstable due to the BSG.16 image that is offset from the two other images. The shift is a static bias and the root causes are not explained.

Table 5-8: Multi-temporal geometric accuracy results (Salon).

Reference Image	BSG.16 2019-10-05	BSG.16 2019-10-05	BSG.17 2019-10-11
Working Image	BSG.17 2019-10-11	BSG.18 2019-10-14	BSG.18 2019-10-14
PAN Band sample (#Pixel)	3016	2737	5872
Easting Error Mean (m)	5.60	5.87	0.07
Northing Error Mean (m)	-3.59	-3.43	-0.20
Easting Error Std (m)	1.52	1.85	1.94
Northing Error Std (m)	1.71	1.94	2.11
Easting Error RMS (m)	5.80	6.15	1.94
Northing Error RMS (m)	3.98	3.94	2.12
Root Mean Square Error (m)	7.03	7.30	2.87
Circular Error @ 90 Percentile (m)	8.01	9.57	4.42
<i>(Error = REF – WORK)</i>			

Geometric distortions affecting BSG.17 / BSG.18 highlighted with a precision above that of the two other twins, can be analysed with the dense image matching report shown in the figures below.

In the radial error image (Figure 5-27 C), the errors are correlated with the terrain relief, as the terrain becomes hilly in the upper part of the region of interest. The Salon-de-Provence airport is flat and, in the middle, the radial error is very close to 0. As observed with statistical distributions (histograms Figure 5-27 A & D), the distributions in both cases are not symmetric; as confirmed with a normality test that is rejected, there is an evident skew.

The distortions remain more pronounced in the line direction (in image coordinates) associated to the across-track direction, considering BSG-103 orbit configuration. Concerning the scatter plot (Figure 5-27 B), the data generally have a fair amount of "scatter" around the peak.

Figure 5-27: Dense Matching Report (BSG.17 / BSG.18).

The question is whether it is possible to improve the geometric processing by using the RPC coefficients provided with the non-orthorectified products. The RPC coefficients set describes a 3D generic geo-referencing model. These have been used together with data from ALOS PRISM DEM and ALOS DEM AW3d30 as reference elevation data sources for ortho processing of the multi temporal dataset (BSG.16, BSG.17, BSG.18). This georeferencing is direct and is not calibrated by using GCP set, as done in the BlackSky processing. The scope of this processing was to analyse the precision, even if there is an accuracy loss (if geolocation bias exists).

The dense image matching report of BSG.17 / BSG.18, by using this processing, is shown in Figure 5-28 below. The symmetry of the statistical distributions of residual errors is better in both directions (mean and median values are now very close). With less amplitude, geometric distortions still exist, essentially pronounced in the line direction (across-track), as observed in the line displacement image Figure 5-29.

Figure 5-28: Dense Matching Report (BSG.17 / BSG.18), RPC georeferencing.

Figure 5-29: Line displacement images, BSG.17 / BSG.18), RPC georeferencing.

This multi-temporal analysis demonstrated that the co-registration of the VHR ortho images (nominal product) is not stable and might depend on the elevation data involved in the processing. The processing is efficient and robust to pointing change, since no major differences have been observed between two images taken with two opposite, extreme pointing angles.

The internal image geometry should be improved by considering the RPC model given in the Level 1B product and a finer-resolution DEM provided by the user. A fine DEM is essential to account for elevation of man-made features, particularly apparent with VHR data. An important requirement would be to provide user with calibrated RPC model, as shown in this experiment, the static bias associated with the RPC is in some cases above 30.0 m, which corresponds to an a-priori geolocation accuracy.

5.6 Image Quality: Signal-to-Noise Ratio

5.6.1 Activity Description Sheet

SNR Accuracy Validation
<i>Inputs</i>
Two Level 1C BlackSky products (ortho)
<i>Description</i>

SNR Accuracy Validation

The Signal-to-Noise Ratio (SNR) has been estimated for each spectral band. The data has been evaluated for a reference radiance corresponding to those of the Libya 4 desert site for the concerned spectral bands. Note that due to the nature of the panchromatic band image, no conversion to radiance measurements has been performed, and for this band, the SNR accuracy has not been estimated.

Outputs

SNR measurement associated to each band, except Panchromatic band.

5.6.2 Introduction

The SNR is an important image quality indicator to assess the potential of data. Visual interpretation of the image does not require high SNR data, even in the presence of noise an operator is able to identify object. However, multispectral image processing requires high SNR values in order to control uncertainties in the measurement as much as possible.

The method proposed herein is simple and is used for two BlackSky products of the same area. The products are from two different dates, 5th October 2019 (20191005) and 7th October 2019 (20191007), acquired with two different satellites.

It is interesting to understand if the SNR results are consistent with those images from similar sensors and if they vary across the constellation. There is no SNR specification proposed by the data provider. Furthermore, it is expected that SNR does not change greatly depending on the spectral band.

5.6.3 Methods and Tools

The SNR is a measure of the mean signal-to-noise ratio. Two types of SNR are typically measured:

- Temporal SNR;
- Spatial SNR.

The basic formulation of the SNR is:

$$SNR = \frac{\mu}{\sigma}$$

Where:

- μ is the mean signal,
- σ is the standard deviation of the signal.

In the frame of the EDAP project, the proposed method estimates the spatial SNR considering statistics over a set of “small windows” (9 pixels by 9 pixels), where by referring to the previous mathematical relationship:

- The “mean signal” is defined as the spatial average of a group of pixels in the “small window”;

- Noise is typically defined as the standard deviation of a region of pixels in the “small window”.

Each spectral band image (radiance measurement) is processed with the modified algorithm initially proposed in [RD-7]. The algorithm has been modified to allow the selection of small windows of uniform image intensity (condition 1), and the selection of small windows mostly located over regions with a flat terrain relief (condition 2).

For conducting the SNR analysis, a uniform / bright scene has to be selected and the Libya-4 site appears to be appropriate for this purpose. The site uniformity increases over small areas, and thus small windows were selected. However, the spatial high frequency image content still exists, specifically at locations of sharp transition (e.g. desert dune summit). To overcome this issue, a dedicated image processing is applied in order to detect high frequency content and filter small windows (image window processing with Sobel operator).

As consequences, to fulfil both conditions, the proposed algorithm considers as input:

- Edge image, obtained with image processing (Sobel operator) to discard area with high frequency content
- Digital Elevation Model data

The different steps of this algorithm can be summarized as follows:

1. Create SNR image, considering as input, image converted to radiance measurements, and iterating on “small windows” to compute SNR,
2. Compute local statistics over 9 pixels x 9 pixels sliding window on the terrain relief data and the image edge response (Sobel Operator),
3. Select the set of “small windows” displaying uniform content and located in flat area
4. Compute the statistical distribution (histogram) of “small windows” $\frac{\mu}{\sigma}$,
5. Location of the peak in the histogram is a measure of the system SNR,
6. Report the SNR value at the peak and the corresponding mean radiance value.

It is worth noting that BlackSky images are not calibrated, and therefore metadata does not include information to convert image digital numbers into top of atmosphere measurements or radiance measurements. Also, a part of the results proposed herein deal with the calibration of BlackSky images.

5.6.4 Region of interest

The region of interest is located over the Libya 4 site; the full geographical area of the BlackSky scene is considered.

5.6.5 Data

5.6.5.1 BlackSky Data acquisition date

- 7 October 2019: BSG-101-20191007-090630-470174 (BSG.11),
- 5 October 2019: BSG-102-20191005-090352-464670 (BSG.10).

5.6.6 Results

5.6.6.1 Conversion to radiance measurements

Libya 4 is a well-known Pseudo Invariant Calibration Site (**PICS**). The BlackSky images have been calibrated by using as reference Landsat 8 / OLI data. Due to the GSD difference between the two sensors, respectively 1.0 m and 30.0 m, the image comparison in view of match up dataset creation and fitting is not straightforward. In particular, effects due to terrain relief should be accounted for and the associated match up discarded.

As shown in Figure 5-30, there is a strong relationship between radiance differences (Landsat 8 – BlackSky) and terrain relief. Major non-linear differences exist in areas located at the edge of dunes where shadows, directional effects and intensity changes are more frequently observed by BlackSky and partially observed, due to convolution, by Landsat 8 / OLI. For these reasons, it is important to discard, from the match up, points located in these areas: fitting statistics are performed for certain classes of elevation, discarding top and edge of dunes (slope).

Figure 5-30: Difference (LS8 – BSG.11) between radiance images (left) and corresponding image of terrain relief (right)

As Input reference, the following data has been considered:

- LC81810402016195MTI00 as radiometric reference,
- ALOS DEM, ALPSMLC30_N028E023_DSM as terrain relief reference.

As shown in Table 5-9 and Figure 5-31, the linear relationship between Landsat 8 data and BlackSky data is not strong but remains acceptable with an adjustment coefficient (R value) between 0.6 and 0.8 depending on the band number and the product.

Table 5-9: Calibration results for the two input products

	slope			intercept ($W/(m^2 \cdot \text{str} \cdot \mu\text{m})$)			R Value
	value	min	max	value	min	max	
BSG.11	0.0636	0.0625	0.0648	117.5674	117.4063	117.7285	0.61
	0.0928	0.0915	0.0941	144.1676	143.9481	144.3872	0.7
	0.0887	0.0874	0.0901	167.3097	167.0557	167.5637	0.68
BSG.10	0.0859	0.0848	0.0871	114.6979	114.5525	114.8536	0.7
	0.1346	0.1333	0.1358	134.9404	134.7178	135.1631	0.81
	0.1245	0.1231	0.1259	155.6951	155.3920	155.998	0.77

Figure 5-31: Landsat 8 / BlackSky match up graphics per band (BSG.11), before correction (left) and after correction (right).

5.6.6.2 SNR Accuracy

Table 5-10 lists the SNR results for the two products and for the three spectral bands. The SNR result is given for a reference radiance value.

For the first product (BSG.11), variations in SNR between bands is not significant, but for the second product (BSG.10), greater differences are observed, particularly between the

Red and Blue bands. This may be due to the quality of BSG-102 (BSG.10) images that exhibit more “dead detector” flags as shown in the composition in Figure 5-32. It results in higher standard deviation over uniform areas and consequently, a degraded SNR. Furthermore, both observations are not exactly in the same region.

Table 5-10: SNR results

Scene Id	Band	SNR Value	Radiance Value
BSG-101-20191007-090630-470174 (BSG.11)	Blue	160.9	126.53
	Green	160.9	159.25
	Red	159.9	183.55
BSG-102-20191005-090352-464670 (BSG.10)	Blue	134.0	126.46
	Green	135.0	159.55
	Red	149.9	184.06

Figure 5-32: Composition of two BlackSky images (BLUE) showing several dead detectors in BSG-102 (BSG.10) shown by the arrow

Figure 5-33 and Figure 5-34 below shows the $\frac{\mu}{\sigma}$, histogram computed for each spectral band (RGB) for the 7 October and 5 October products, respectively. The peak in the histogram is a measure of the system SNR.

BSG-101-20191007-090630-470174

BSG-101-20191007-090630-470174

BSG-101-20191007-090630-470174

Figure 5-33: The $\frac{\mu}{\sigma}$, histogram computed for each spectral band (Top: Red, Middle: Green, Bottom: Blue) for the product BSG-101-20191007-090630-470174 (BSG.11)

BSG-102-20191005-090352-464670

BSG-102-20191005-090352-464670

Figure 5-34: The $\frac{\mu}{\sigma}$, histogram computed for each spectral band (Top: Red, Middle: Green, Bottom: Blue) for the product BSG-102-20191005-090352-464670 (BSG.10)

5.7 Image Quality: Modulation Transfer Function

5.7.1 Activity Description Sheet

SNR Accuracy Validation
<i>Inputs</i>
Two non-ortho BlackSky products observed over Salon-de-Provence Airport (MTF checkboard target)
<i>Description</i>
The MTF measurements are based on the slanted edge approach as described in [RD-8] (Telespazio method)
<i>Outputs</i>
MTF quality associated to each band

5.7.2 Introduction

The spatial resolution of a sensor has traditionally been a difficult concept to define, but all would agree that it is inextricably linked to the GSD and Instantaneous Field of View (IFOV) of an imaging sensor system.

As a measure of the geospatial quality of imagery, the MTF of the system is often used along with the SNR. The MTF is often used as a measure of image sharpness. This important parameter for image quality has to be checked on each orbit in order to be sure that launch vibrations, transition from air to vacuum, or thermal state have not degraded the sharpness of the images [RD-8].

5.7.3 Methods and Tools

The slant-edge method presented herein has been developed and operated in the context of the ESA contribution to the ALOS PRISM calibration campaign [RD-9]. The different steps of the algorithm are depicted within Figure 5-35 below and discussed thereafter.

Figure 5-35: Slant-edge method – algorithm steps.

The input MTF target is a checkboard image observed in all spectral bands and illustrated in Figure 5-39 and Figure 5-40. The region of interest includes edge transitions, and nearly-vertical / nearly-horizontal edges are used to estimate MTF in the along-track (**AL**) / across-track (**AC**) direction or axis.

The method estimates, for any spectral channels the MTF associated with the complete system response. The MTF is derived from computation of the ESF and Line Spread Function (**LSF**). These curves are accompanied with quality indicator metrics, such as Relative Edge Response (**RER**), SNR and Full Width at Half Maximum (**FWHM**).

5.7.3.1 Edge Modelling

The true MTF is defined normal to the edge. If the edge is slanted, MTF is calculated from the average of many sampling phases.

The construction of the ESF is inspired from [RD-10] where sampling phases are collected for a given orientation of the target. The edge modelling step is the estimation of the orientation of the target. As shown in Figure 5-36, for each image row included in the region depicted with rectangular form (Upper Left image), a parametric function is fitted in order to estimate the sub-pixel location of the inflection point. Based on the set of inflection point-sub pixels location found, a least squares method is used to estimate an overall orientation angle (Upper right image). The per-row interpolated edge functions (Lower Left image) are checked and discarded in case of noise. In the figure hereafter (Lower Left image), it is observed that the form of the curve changes depending on the image row.

Figure 5-36: Slant-edge method – edge modelling output.

5.7.3.2 Edge Spread Function Construction

The MTF method is very sensitive to noise and the orientation of edge should be accurately known. As mentioned before, a single image row is not sufficient to capture the various pixel phases accounting for aliasing and phase effects etc. The super-resolved target image is built applying the same approach for each image row and following these stages;

- Projection of each image pixel onto a line perpendicular to edge applying rotation angle estimate in the previous step, the method proposed by Kohm [RD-10] is used;
- Resampling of the pixel position in the new projection system, within bin of $\frac{1}{4}$ pixel width.

Figure 5-37 shows the super-resolved target image with edge transitions that are now perfectly aligned. Depending on the expected direction (along / across axis), it is possible to define for each bin, the intensity value (pixel phase) of the ESF. By nature, in the final ESF, some bins can be left empty. It is therefore important to maximize the number of processed lines, for BlackSky approximately 61 rows of over sample target are used.

Because some bins are left empty, at this point the sampling of the ESF data points are not uniformly distributed. The Locally Estimated Scatterplot Smoothing (**LOESS**) curve fitting algorithm (locally weighted non-parametric regression fitting using a 2nd order polynomial) is used to resample the data to uniformly spaced sample points. There is no a priori ESF model fit to the data points (parametric approach) as commonly done in the community.

Figure 5-37: Super Resolved Target (0.25 pixel bin).

5.7.3.3 MTF Calculation

The final stage is to compute the MTF by using a derivative method: computing the finite difference approximation of the uniformly spaced ESF to produce the LSF.

The LSF may contain high frequency noise, amplified by the derivative method. A local smoothing with fourth order Savitsky-Golay filtering is applied (window size is 11 bins) to remove outliers. At the end, a Hann window is applied to the ESF (three-term weighted average smoothing technique) and a smooth LSF is obtained.

The main outputs of the method are shown in Figure 5-38 below. The ESF, LSF and MTF curves are carefully checked. An additional figure (Lower left in the figure) is used to check LOESS interpolation, and in particular, the intensity estimated for all empty bins.

Figure 5-38: (a) Standard outputs of the MTF methods, LSF produced with the first derivative of ESF curve.

5.7.4 Region of interest

The region of interest is Salon-de-Provence Airport, France. The MTF target seen by the BlackSky satellite is shown in the figures below. The convention used to report MTF assessment is as follows:

- VL – Down Along track Edge, Vertical Edge from low to high luminance,
- VH – Up Along track Edge, Vertical Edge from high to low luminance,
- HL – Right Across track Edge, Horizontal Edge from low to high luminance,
- HH – Left Across track Edge, Horizontal Edge from high to low luminance.

This convention is important in order to understand the results and they are depicted in the band 1 image of the target in Figure 5-39 below. Visual inspection of target images shows that the image quality differs depending on spectral bands and observation dates.

Figure 5-39: MTF Target in the BSG-103-20191005 image

Figure 5-40: MTF Target in the BSG-103-20191014 image

Note that due to flying direction of the BSG-103 satellite, the along track direction is from West to East.

5.7.5 Data

- 5 October 2019: BSG-103-20191005-123447-465075 (BSG.16)
- 14 October 2019: BSG-103-20191014-083533-496003 (BSG.18)

There are important considerations to note regarding the input data: the BlackSky data delivered to EDAP is pansharpened data to ease visual inspection (standard product). This remote sensing data has been acquired with Bayer sensors. For Bayer sensors, each raw pixel represents a single colour in RGRGRG sequence, converted into usable image files. The processing uses a de-mosaicing programme performing several functions with notably, the addition of a gamma curve and tonal response curve. In addition, the noise is reduced and image is sharpened. All these processing results may interfere with the MTF measurements reported herein: The de-mosaicing present in all cameras that use Colour Filter Array involve nonlinear processing, the MTF measurements proposed herein included effects of this processing.

It is worth noting that a strong noise signal affects the PAN band (band 4) as shown in Figure 5-39, Figure 5-40. For this reason, the PAN band image dated of October 14 has been discarded from the analyses.

5.7.6 Results

5.7.6.1 Overall results

The MTF analysis confirms visual inspection outputs and allows for a characterisation of the PSF and MTF.

As shown in the figures below (Figure 5-41, Figure 5-42), whatever the spectral band, the MTF curves are almost the same, which confirms an efficient de-mosaicing process. It is worth noting that theoretically, in Bayer Colour Filter Array sensor, the effective horizontal and Vertical Nyquist frequency for red and blue pixels is half that of the green. In this assessment, we did not observe this assessment, meaning that de-mosaicing is performed nominally.

Looking at the images, the contrast of images dated of 20191014 (BSG.18) is better than the contrast of image dated of 20191005 (BSG.16). Comparing observation dates, the MTF curves associated with 20191014 were always higher and this is for all directions. The BlackSky image contrast is always increased at image edge boundaries due to use of a sharpening process.

The sharpening process applied to BSG.18 is stronger. It is particularly visible with VL, HL MTF curves, which tends to increase around Nyquist frequency. Another indicator is the “MTF50” which is the spatial frequency where image contrast is half (50%). This value is in most cases always higher for BSG.18 compared to BSG.16.

When overdone, the side effects of sharpening is the presence of edge artefacts (“halos”), particularly well-illustrated with the ESF figures shown from Section 5.7.6.2.1 - 5.7.6.2.7. Furthermore, another side effect of sharpening is the aliasing, particularly visible with large MTF response above Nyquist frequency in the case of BSG.18 (all bands) and BSG.16

(PAN band). In some cases, the aliasing issues arise from the sensor, but we do not observe “Moire” patterns (introduction of high frequencies into low frequencies) in the imagery, except for BSG.16 (PAN band). The aliasing due to pan-sharpening is also visible in the ESF that appear jagged (discontinuities) in some cases.

The quality of the panchromatic band is degraded, with presence of noise in the homogeneous parts of the target.

The filtering applied to enhance the image contrast is always visible in the three ESF, LSF and MTF measurements. The filtering configuration is adaptive and results differ depending on the observation date and observation geometry. Furthermore, this processing makes it difficult to interpret for qualification of the whole system (estimation of the on-board parameter).

As shown in the table below, the SNR associated to the results is quite low, and slightly below the threshold of 30 specified in [RD-8]. This is due to noise in the uniform part of the target. From an accuracy specification point of view, the MTF at Nyquist is always above 0.05 and it is totally in agreement with what is expected from this kind of VHR system. The FWHM is always below 1.5 m for RGB bands and 2.0 m for PAN band.

It is worth noting that the MTF results are degraded in the along-track direction compared to the across-track direction (this is due to motion blur).

Figure 5-41: The product comparison of MTF Curves (HH, HL, VH, VL) for BGR spectral bands.

Figure 5-42: The MTF Curves (HH,HL,VH,VL) for PAN spectral band (20191005).

The quantitative results of the MTF methods are given in the two tables below.

Table 5-11: Spatial resolution analysis, BGR spectral bands results

Product Id	Direction	BAND1 (BLUE)				BAND2 (GREEN)				BAND3 (RED)			
		FWHM (m)	MTF	SNR	RER	FWHM (m)	MTF	SNR	RER	FWHM (m)	MTF	SNR	RER
BSG-103 - 20191005	AC/HH	1	0.13	8.94	244.94	1.50	0.08	10.76	259.99	1.25	0.16	10.63	250.49
	AC/HL	1.5	0.11	12.89	216.63	1.75	0.08	13.59	224.21	1.75	0.12	18.96	221.85
	AL/VH	0.5	0.08	13.23	211.79	1.00	0.08	20.73	216.09	1.00	0.11	16.26	214.06
	AL/VL	1.75	0.08	16.51	190.62	2.00	0.07	19.77	193.54	1.75	0.12	15.06	186.51
BSG-103 - 20191014	AC/HH	1.25	0.12	15.16	189.58	2.00	0.13	16.97	191.92	1.50	0.16	15.88	189.90
	AC/HL	1.5	0.13	21.83	170.57	1.25	0.13	19.68	178.21	1.25	0.15	24.49	181.06
	AL/VH	1.5	0.11	16.28	193.65	0.75	0.12	21.47	205.40	1.25	0.16	15.73	220.66
	AL/VL	1.75	0.12	19.29	175.80	1.75	0.16	13.52	189.36	1.75	0.18	16.98	192.29

Table 5-12: Spatial resolution analysis, PAN spectral bands results

Product Id	Direction	BAND4 (PAN)			
		FWHM (m)	MTF	SNR	RER
BSG-103 -20191005	AC/HH	2.00	0.17	8.62	-313.32
	AC/HL	1.50	0.15	11.98	316.44
	AL/VH	1.50	0.04	10.94	-279.32
	AL/VL	2.00	0.05	13.48	255.35

5.7.6.2 Detailed results and analysis

The section herein shows, for both BlackSky products, the computed ESF, LSF and MTF curves used as input to compute MTF curve and used to estimate MTF at Nyquist frequency, RER, SNR and FWHM reported in the previous section.

The ESF curves shows, in most cases, the presence of two “halos”, respectively in low and high luminance levels, as a result of a strong sharpening.

The LSF curves are in general asymmetric, depending on the direction of luminance change; from high to low (h) or low to high (l). The magnitude of the “halos” is more important in the (h) direction. A simple sharpening algorithm considers a window of neighbored pixels, the response to sharpening process linearly depends on the intensity values.

On the down-side, the sharpening process increases noise, it becomes evident for pixels of low intensity level. It can be assumed that an “unsharp” mask (smoothing filter) is applied locally to remove these unexpected effects. The filtering performs well over uniform areas of high intensity and does not cover areas of low intensities.

As shown with LSF shape, the sharpening process, image enhancement, is probably performed in the Fourier domain, by applying a threshold: the LSF, (spatial domain) is in some cases very close to the shape of a sinus cardinal.

Discontinuities (break) in the ESF / LSF curves are also observed in case of the Vertical Edge from low to high luminance (“along-track direction (HI)”), Section 5.7.6.2.1. This break is an aliasing issue as a result of the pan-sharpening process. Visual inspection shows evidence of low pass filtering is applied in the image to limit aliasing issue, conversely, smoothing degrades the image contrast, but the first objective of pan sharpening remains to enhance the image contrast.

5.7.6.2.1 BSG-103-20191005-123447-465075 (Blue Band)

5.7.6.2.2 BSG-103-20191005-123447-465075 (Green Band)

5.7.6.2.3 BSG-103-20191005-123447-465075 (Red Band)

5.7.6.2.4 BSG-103-20191005-123447-465075 (PAN Band)

5.7.6.2.5 BSG-103-20191014-083533-496003 (Blue Band)

5.7.6.2.6 BSG-103-20191014-083533-496003 (Green Band)

5.7.6.2.7 BSG-103-20191014-083533-496003 (Red Band)

6. CONCLUSIONS

The BlackSky products include VHR images (1.0m GSD) with a primary usage dedicated to object recognition and object extraction. The downstream applications of these data are specific, and the related Earth Observation product has been developed accordingly. The image data are characterised by post-processing which enhances contrast. Conversely, modification of the signal in such a way prevents delivery of physical measurements with radiometric calibration applied.

The overall data quality aspects of the products have been addressed. It has not been possible to compare these third-party validation results with those from other sources, because no technical documentation on the mission is freely opened to the user community. The only input considered was the product user guide, subject to a “non-disclosure agreement”.

With this framework considered, the EDAP analysis presented herein focused on following items:

- The product format and UDM mask;
- The image fidelity;
- The image quality including the SNR and the MTF;
- The geometrical performance of the end user product.

BlackSky, through e-GEOS, delivered an input sample dataset including data observed over EDAP validation test sites. Each product reference has been delivered as processed into both Level 1B (non-ortho) and into Level 1C (ortho) product processing levels.

The product metadata are embedded into the JSON file format: few parameters are reported in the format but essential information exists. An additional UDM accompanies the image data that is mostly consistent regarding anomaly flagging and cloud detection.

The potential of BlackSky imagery in the context of object detection, object recognition and object identification has been analysed by adopting an image interpretability approach. The results are correct, and almost all selected objects can be recovered and extracted with less accuracy compared to the same object extracted with a reference image (Pleiades). This exercise has given the opportunity to observe that the quality of BlackSky strongly varies depending on the observation date and the observing platform. Furthermore, the panchromatic band is not appropriate for visual inspection because of noise contamination.

The detection/extraction of objects in an image becomes more accurate when geolocation accuracy is correct. Checking the geometry of BlackSky images has been performed by using EDAP test fields covered with geometric reference material (GCPs from GPS test field survey and a raster reference (SPOT-5)).

Within this scope, the accuracy of Level 1B, Level 1C images has been evaluated. Like the instruments on board Planet DOVE and DOVE-R missions, the BlackSky sensor is a 2D array with a colour filter array (Bayer). In the BlackSky processing, consecutive images are not stitched together to create an image covering a larger geographical extent. This approach prevents issues regarding geometric co-registration of the 2D array images, as observed in the case of DOVE and DOVE-R.

Absolute, interband and multi-temporal accuracy assessments have been performed. In all cases the absolute geolocation of image geometry is degraded with an important offset within 15.0 m on both easting / northing directions knowing that the Level 1C accuracy specification is 20.0 m CE90.

However, one can note that the internal geometry appears stable. Due to the planimetric shift and the use of a coarse DEM (SRTM), geometric distortions in the image are strongly correlated with the terrain relief. This situation might be improved by considering the RPC model provided in the Level 1B and a finer DEM. Unfortunately, the RPC model is not calibrated, and the planimetric accuracy as a results of georeferencing with RPCs is worse compared to Level 1C. Finally, to fully utilise the data, the user should be able to calibrate RPCs themselves.

When considering more appropriate reference data, we showed that the geolocation accuracy of products can be improved, but it requires more investigation.

Concerning the interband registration of multispectral bands, it is very good, however one can note a static offset between the panchromatic and multispectral bands.

Finally, the multi-temporal analysis confirms assertions given in the part dedicated to absolute; the ortho processing remains stable and accuracy does not change so much with time.

The added value of these products is the image enhancement processing, intended to support the visual inspection task.

The post-processing applied to enhance the image quality has an impact on the overall EDAP methodology. The BlackSky image is generally sharp with high contrast (except for panchromatic). The difficulty is to find the most appropriate trade off to preserve low frequency information dipping into the noise. In the visual inspection and geometric assessment, it has been observed that some parts of objects were missing because of filtering. Furthermore, the geometric assessment based on image matching was difficult to tune because information to be matched is generally poor.

The image quality parameters SNR and MTF have been assessed by using two distinct methods. The classic slanted edge method has been used to estimate MTF for images observed at two different dates over checkerboard targets at the Salon, France site.

Considering the edge profile (ESF), a non-parametric approach for ESF and LSF modelling has been applied. The use of parametric model should have been convenient. However, it was actually impossible to fit a model because of sharpening.

The overall results are within expectations with respect to the system specifications; as mentioned, the instrument includes a Bayer Colour Filter Array system.

This analysis shows the drawbacks of the use of adaptive image processing, similar to the drawbacks associated with the use of personal digital cameras or cell phone cameras. Also, over time, the image quality parameters are not fully stable. One panchromatic image was not assessed because the quality was degraded. The main reason is the use of adaptive processing that finally depends on pixel intensities.

The adaptive processing is used to enhance the image contrast with sharpening. The effect of sharpening is almost systematically observed in the ESF curves (presence of “halos”). The sharpening looks to not be performed systematically, it is generally calibrated with a threshold and it depends on the intensity difference between two consecutive pixels. The drawbacks of this approach are to increase the noise in the image, the reason why the SNR of the method is low.

To limit aliasing, a dedicated low pass filtering is also applied. To avoid degrading the contrast too much, the parametrisation of the anti-aliasing should be carefully performed. As discussed before, the ESF / MTF curves show the presence of aliasing respectively with discontinuities in the edge profile and with a higher magnitude of MTF above Nyquist frequency.

The analysis confirms observations arising from visual inspection and SNR assessment activities. It has not been possible to estimate a global MTF model accounting for optic / detector motion transfer function. In this scope, it is important to point out that the metadata should be improved to report more parameters regarding camera properties at the time of acquisition, as done with the Exchangeable Image File Format (**EXIF**) format⁶.

⁶ https://fr.wikipedia.org/wiki/Exchangeable_image_file_format

APPENDIX A BlackSky Product Breakdown Structure

The Figures below show the BlackSky product Breakdown Structure

Figure 6-1: Tier 1 PBS folder for BlackSky products

Figure 6-2: Tier 2 PBS folder for BlackSky products within BSG-PRODUCT-ID-ortho.

Figure 6-3: Tier 2 PBS folder for BlackSky products within BSG-PRODUCT-ID-non-ortho

Figure 6-4: Tier 2 PBS folder for BlackSky products within BSG-PRODUCT-ID-nitf-ortho

Figure 6-5: Tier 2 PBS folder for BlackSky products within BSG-PRODUCT-ID-nitf-non-ortho

 BSG-PRODUCT-ID_ortho_b1
 BSG-PRODUCT-ID_ortho_b1.tif.aux

Figure 6-6: Tier 2 PBS folder for BlackSky products within B_RED

 BSG-PRODUCT-ID_ortho_b2
 BSG-PRODUCT-ID_ortho_b2.tif.aux

Figure 6-7: Tier 2 PBS folder for BlackSky products within B_GREEN

 BSG-PRODUCT-ID_ortho_b3
 BSG-PRODUCT-ID_ortho_b3.tif.aux

Figure 6-8: Tier 2 PBS folder for BlackSky products within B_BLUE

APPENDIX B List of BlackSky products used

Table 6-1: EDAP BlackSky Test Data Set

EDAP ID	Product ID	Off Nadir Angle	Cloud Cover (%)	Sun Elevation	Satellite Elevation	Sun Azimuth	Satellite Azimuth	Test Site
BSG.1	BSG-103-20191005-105550-464915	27.2	0	41.160	60.184	168.989	288.514	La Crau
BSG.2	BSG-103-20191011-085000-484115	18.2	2.770	28.218	68.291	134.428	356.756	La Crau
BSG.3	BSG-101-20191015-102859-499986	20.7	0.060	36.356	65.644	162.284	5.514	La Crau
BSG.4	BSG-102-20191024-104036-525146	15.8	2.770	33.814	69.349	166.961	259.917	La Crau
BSG.5	BSG-104-20191025-094224-528654	28.2	0	29.702	72.653	150.940	340.446	La Crau
BSG.6	BSG-104-20191029-091006-539183	26.5	0.530	25.334	67.030	143.510	315.774	La Crau
BSG.7	BSG-101-20191005-083710-464588	1.1	0	50.101	72.690	49.095	99.811	Le Cap
BSG.8	BSG-101-20191012-085417-488769	25.2	0	55.122	60.213	45.609	300.862	Le Cap
BSG.9	BSG-101-20191012-085437-488770	13.0	0.01	55.169	61.375	45.498	269.859	Le Cap
BSG.10	BSG-102-20191005-090352-464670	22.3	0	52.778	89.253	149.864	51.013	Libya4
BSG.11	BSG-101-20191007-090630-470174	16.4	0.01	52.466	63.761	151.563	223.871	Libya4
BSG.12	BSG-101-20191007-090602-470173	16.8	0.01	52.404	75.611	151.390	285.428	Libya4
BSG.13	BSG-102-20191005-103538-464692	10.8	42.75	39.690	65.069	165.704	289.112	Piedmont
BSG.14	BSG-103-20191005-105633-464916	21.6	1.330	40.390	72.621	172.455	270.606	Piedmont
BSG.15	BSG-101-20191008-101145-472729	21.6	1.149	37.327	72.251	158.876	98.292	Piedmont
BSG.16	BSG-103-20191005-123447-465075	23.0	0	39.362	76.766	201.741	41.283	Salon
BSG.17	BSG-103-20191011-085019-484116	19.2	12.829	28.351	65.058	134.774	30.403	Salon
BSG.18	BSG-103-20191014-083533-496003	14.3	2.619	25.558	65.441	132.135	312.641	Salon
BSG.19	BSG-101-20191005-083642-464587	19.9	0	50.482	66.091	49.568	57.969	Wellington
BSG.20	BSG-104-20191029-160726-539585	8.5	0.129	11.653	82.320	261.413	28.895	Wellington
BSG.21	BSG-104-20191030-155924-541262	12.8	0.009	13.472	74.619	262.175	214.551	Wellington

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